

Gender, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Handbook for cities

IN-HABIT – INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies D6.4 – Gender, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Toolkit and Handbook for Cities

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Disclaimer: The content of this document does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union and in no way anticipates the European Commission's future policy in this area. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the author(s).

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Version	Status	Date	Contributor/part ner	Summary of changes
1	Final	31 st of August, 2025	University of Turin and University of Reading	
2	Revised	21 January 2026	University of Turin and University of Reading	Introduction of standalone Toolkit and revisions requested by reviewers

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Toolkit overview and guidance for use

This toolkit is designed to support policy-makers, public administrations, and urban practitioners in the practical integration of Gender Equality, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (GDEI) into urban governance, policy-making, and evaluation processes. Its purpose is not to introduce new principles or normative commitments, but to provide a **clear and usable decision-support framework** that helps translate GDEI objectives into concrete institutional actions, policy choices, and measurable results.

The toolkit is grounded in a new **Gendered Landscape (GL) framework** developed within the INHABIT project. The framework conceptualises gender and intersecting inequalities in urban contexts through three interconnected pillars:

- **Pillar 1 – Institutions:** governance structures, mandates, resources, accountability mechanisms, and data practices;
- **Pillar 2 – Policies:** the design, implementation, and delivery of policies, programmes, and services, including budgeting, procurement, and participatory processes;
- **Pillar 3 – Outcomes:** the measurement and evaluation of results in terms of wellbeing, access, and inequality reduction for different population groups.

The toolkit adopts an **iterative logic**. Institutional arrangements shape policy choices; policies generate outcomes; and evidence on outcomes feeds back into institutional reform and policy redesign. The pillars should therefore be understood as part of a continuous learning cycle rather than as a fixed sequence.

Structure of the toolkit

The toolkit is organised around two complementary elements: **flowcharts** and **template tables**.

Cross-pillar orientation flowchart. The first flowchart operates at a **cross-pillar level**. Its function is to help users identify *which pillar* is most relevant to their current decision, problem, or objective. By answering a small set of high-level questions, users are guided towards Pillar 1, 2, or 3, without yet engaging with specific tools or templates.

Pillar-specific flowcharts. The subsequent flowcharts focus on each pillar separately. These flowcharts guide users **inside the pillar**, through a structured sequence of questions formulated in terms of objectives and needs (e.g. anticipating impacts, strengthening governance routines, evaluating outcomes). Their purpose is to help users identify:

- which type of template is most appropriate for a given objective;
- when multiple templates may be needed;

Template tables Each pillar-specific flowchart is followed by a table that provides a concise and standardised overview of the templates associated with that pillar. For each template, the table summarises:

- its core purpose and the problem it addresses;
- the main inputs required (e.g. data, stakeholder engagement, internal coordination);
- the key outputs it produces;
- the organisational capacities needed for implementation;
- references to further guidance and source documents.

The flowcharts and tables are designed to be used together: the flowcharts support *navigation and choice*, while the tables support *understanding and implementation*.

How to use the toolkit

The toolkit is modular and flexible. It does not prescribe a single pathway, nor does it assume a common level of institutional maturity across cities or organisations.

A typical use involves four steps:

1. Identify the concrete decision, problem, or objective at hand.
2. Use the cross-pillar flowchart to identify the most relevant pillar.

3. Follow the pillar-specific flowchart to identify suitable templates.
4. Consult the corresponding table to assess feasibility, requirements, and expected outputs.

Selecting a template does not imply that the process ends there. Several objectives may lead to the use of multiple templates, either sequentially or in parallel. Conversely, users may decide to stop at an intermediate stage if resources, mandate, or capacity are limited.

Scope and sources

The tables provide **operational summaries**, not full methodological manuals. When more detailed guidance is required, users are referred to:

- The **Gender Diversity and Inclusion Handbook**, which presents the Gendered Landscape framework, its application across the three pillars, and the overall logic of the toolkit;
- the original reports and toolkits from which each template is drawn (e.g. EIGE guidance, URBACT and Cities Alliance resources, World Bank toolkits, evaluation handbooks).

Overall, the toolkit is intended to help move from general GDEI commitments to **coherent, evidence-informed, and actionable choices**, adapted to different urban contexts and stages of institutional development.

Pillar 1 — Table

Pillar	Template	Template – where it comes from	Operational steps (strategic sequence + concrete outputs)	Tools	Roles & responsibilities (RACI: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed)	Suggested Timing	Required capacities (minimum viable + recommended)	KPIs (inputs → outputs → outcomes; plus disaggregation)
Pillar I — Institutions	Institutional GDEI Index & Survey		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define scope: city/department/project boundary + stakeholder list. 2) Administer the Institutional Landscape survey to key stakeholders. 3) Clean and code responses; compute 6 dimension scores. 4) Produce outputs: (i) dimension indexes; (ii) radar diagram; (iii) SWOT (strengths/weaknesses by dimension). 5) Validate results with an internal workshop; agree priority gaps. 6) Convert gaps into an institutional action plan (who/what/when) and publish a short accountability note. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sampling: include political leadership, line departments, service providers, HR, procurement, budgeting, data/IT, plus external actors (CSOs, community reps, academia). ▪ Survey ops: assign a coordinator; run 2 reminders; keep a data dictionary; ensure anonymisation if needed. ▪ Indexing: standardise answers into numeric scales per dimension; document thresholds; compute sub-scores then aggregate. ▪ Visuals: radar diagram per city/department; add confidence notes (n respondents) to avoid over-precision. ▪ SWOT: use dimension scores + qualitative comments; translate into 5–10 actionable institutional reforms. 	<p>R — GDEI focal point / equality officer (survey coordinator; compiles evidence).</p> <p>A — City manager / deputy mayor (authorises scope; signs-off results).</p> <p>C — HR, legal, budgeting, procurement, data office, line departments; external CSO advisory group.</p> <p>I — Wider municipal staff, elected council, citizens (summary outputs).</p>	<p>Minimum: 4–6 weeks (survey + basic index + radar).</p> <p>Standard: 8–10 weeks (+ SWOT workshop + action plan draft).</p> <p>Extended: 12–16 weeks (+ repeat survey in sub-units; public consultation).</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1 coordinator (0.2–0.4 FTE) ▪ survey tool (Forms/Qualtrics) ▪ basic Excel skills ▪ one data person for index build <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ dedicated GDEI unit ▪ data analyst ▪ facilitation skills for workshops ▪ stakeholder engagement capacity ▪ political sponsorship and communications support 	<p>Inputs: % departments completing survey; # stakeholders engaged (by type).</p> <p>Outputs: 6-dimension index scores; radar diagram published; # priority reforms agreed.</p> <p>Outcomes: adoption of institutional reforms (e.g., creation of GDEI unit; data collection protocols).</p> <p>Disaggregation: department, governance level, stakeholder type; where possible by gender/diversity of leadership.</p>
Pillar I — Institutions	Participatory Gender Audit	OSCE – Participatory Gender Audits of Parliaments	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Secure mandate + audit objectives; agree on audit scope (institution/unit). 2) Set up audit team + reference group; agree on evidence plan. 3) Collect evidence: document review, interviews, surveys, focus groups. 4) Analyse findings vs standards; identify gaps + good practices. 5) Validate findings with the institution; finalise audit report. 6) Co-develop an action plan with responsibilities, deadlines, and monitoring approach. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evidence pack: policies, HR data, recruitment/promotion stats, training logs, budget lines, complaints mechanisms. ▪ Interview guides mapped to themes: leadership commitment, culture, decision processes, accountability. ▪ ‘Participation’ mechanism: mixed groups (staff + elected members + unions/associations) to co-interpret findings. ▪ Deliverables: (i) audit report with scored findings; (ii) action plan with quick wins (0–3 months) and structural reforms (6–24 months). 	<p>R — Audit team lead (internal or external) + data analyst.</p> <p>A — Secretary General / City manager / Council President (institutional mandate).</p> <p>C — HR, unions/staff reps, legal, department heads; civil society observers if allowed.</p> <p>I — all staff (internal comms); public summary where appropriate.</p>	<p>Minimum: 6–8 weeks (small unit; light evidence).</p> <p>Standard: 10–14 weeks (full institution; validation workshops).</p> <p>Extended: 4–6 months (multi-entity audit + follow-up monitoring design).</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ trained facilitators for participatory sessions ▪ access to internal HR/budget data ▪ qualitative analysis capacity <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ external audit expertise ▪ safe channels for sensitive testimonies ▪ ability to track action plan implementation 	<p>Inputs: # audit participants; diversity of participants; % evidence sources obtained.</p> <p>Outputs: audit report delivered; # recommendations; % recommendations with owners/deadlines.</p> <p>Outcomes: implementation rate of action plan items; staff perceptions of institutional commitment (repeat pulse survey).</p>

Pillar	Template	Template – where it comes from	Operational steps (strategic sequence + concrete outputs)	Tools	Roles & responsibilities (RACI: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed)	Suggested Timing	Required capacities (minimum viable + recommended)	KPIs (inputs → outputs → outcomes; plus disaggregation)
Pillar I — Institutions	GDEI mainstreaming Architecture	OECD – Toolkit for Mainstreaming and Implementing GDEI 2023 EIGE - Institutional mainstreaming tools	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Establish formal mandate: GDEI strategy + monitoring mechanism. 2) Set institutional structures: central GDEI unit + network of gender focal points in line departments. 3) Define accountability chain: reporting cycles, KPI ownership, escalation route. 4) Resource it: budget lines, staffing, capacity development plan. 5) Integrate into core processes: policy cycle, budget cycle, procurement, HR. 6) Publish a governance 'architecture' diagram and annual progress report. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create an 'architecture map': who owns strategy, who does analysis (GIA/GRB), who collects data, who reports. ▪ Draft Terms of Reference for gender focal points (minimum: 5–10% role time + training + reporting templates). ▪ Build a capacity plan: baseline training + advanced modules (GIA, GRB, GRPP, data). ▪ Hard-wire reporting: quarterly dashboard review, annual public report, and budget hearing input. ▪ Use a checklist/self-assessment to identify weak links (e.g., vague roles, input-only indicators). 	<p>R — Central GDEI unit leads architecture map + training + reporting.</p> <p>A — Top leadership (mayor/city manager) owns the strategy and signs annual report.</p> <p>C — Line departments (focal points), budget office, procurement, HR, data office.</p> <p>I — Council, civil society advisory group, public.</p>	<p>Minimum: 1–2 months (design governance map + ToRs).</p> <p>Standard: 3–6 months (appoint focal points + training + first dashboard).</p> <p>Extended: 12 months (full integration in budget/procurement cycles + first annual report).</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ leadership buy-in ▪ 1–2 staff in central unit ▪ basic data/indicator skills <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ multi-disciplinary team (policy + data + procurement + comms) ▪ training budget ▪ data infrastructure for sex-disaggregated and intersectional statistics 	<p>Inputs: existence of strategy/mandate; # focal points appointed; training completion rates.</p> <p>Outputs: % policies screened with GIA; % budget lines tagged; procurement tenders with gender clauses.</p> <p>Outcomes: improved GDEI indicators (link to Pillar 3 KPIs) and reduced policy blind spots.</p>
Pillar I — Institutions	GDEI Action Plan (GEAP) — including Institutional Action Plan	EIGE – Gender Equality Action Plans (GEAPs) OSCE – Participatory Gender Audits (action-planning and follow-up guidance) OECD – Toolkit for Mainstreaming and Implementing Gender Equality (implementation and monitoring practices)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Conduct a GDEI institutional assessment (survey and/or participatory audit). 2) Translate diagnostic findings into a ranked backlog of institutional reforms (governance, HR, budgeting/procurement, data). 3) Develop and formally adopt the GDEI Action Plan (GEAP): objectives, measures, owners, timelines, resources, KPIs. 4) Implement reforms through an Institutional Action Plan (owners, milestones, deliverables, monitoring log). 5) Monitor progress through periodic reviews and KPI tracking. 6) Conduct GDEI-responsive evaluation and update the GEAP cycle (revise/scale/adjust). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Diagnostic inputs: institutional survey results and/or participatory audit evidence. ▪ GDEI Action Plan template (one measure per line: problem, action, owner, budget, timeline, KPI). ▪ Institutional Action Plan and monitoring log (milestones, status, dependencies). ▪ Reporting templates (internal dashboard and public-facing summary). ▪ Evaluation criteria and learning loop feeding into the next planning cycle. 	<p>R — Equality Unit / GDEI mainstreaming team coordinates assessment, planning, implementation tracking, and evaluation.</p> <p>A — Top leadership (Mayor/City Manager/Director-General) mandates and approves the GEAP and ensures resources.</p> <p>C — HR, Finance/Budget, Procurement, Legal, Data/IT, department heads, staff representatives/unions.</p> <p>I — All staff; city council/board; civil society advisory groups; public (via summary reporting).</p>	<p>Minimum: 8–12 weeks (rapid assessment, drafting, and formal adoption; initial monitoring setup).</p> <p>Standard: 3–4 months (robust assessment, consultation, costed measures, monitoring indicators).</p> <p>Extended: 6–9 months (if new data systems, broader engagement, or complex organisation).</p> <p>Plan horizon: multi-year (typically 3–4 years), with annual monitoring and end-term evaluation.</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ access to HR/administrative data (sex-disaggregated where possible) ▪ a coordinator/team to draft measures and manage a basic monitoring tracker ▪ facilitation and consultation capacity <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ gender and intersectional expertise for institutional transformation ▪ budgeting and costing skills to resource measures ▪ evaluation competence for GDEI-responsive learning ▪ communications capacity to sustain engagement and accountability 	<p>Inputs: staff time and budget allocated to GEAP measures; # departments with a nominated measure owner.</p> <p>Outputs: % measures delivered on time; # measures completed; monitoring and progress reports produced.</p> <p>Outcomes (institutional): improved gender balance in decision-making and leadership; reduced gender pay gap; increased GDEI training coverage; improved staff-perception indicators.</p> <p>Disaggregation: by department/unit; by staff category/grade; intersectional where feasible.</p>

Pillar 2

Diagnostic questions. If the answer is **no**, use the linked template(s) to address the gap.

[Go to Pillars' descriptions](#)

[Go to Pillar 1](#)

[Go to Pillar 3](#)

Pillar 2 — Table

Pillar	Template	Template – where it comes from	Operational steps (strategic sequence + concrete outputs)	Tools	Roles & responsibilities (RACI: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed)	Suggested Timing	Required capacities (minimum viable + recommended)	KPIs (inputs → outputs → outcomes; plus disaggregation)
Pillar II — Policies	Gender Impact Assessment (GIA)	EIGE – Gender Impact Assessment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Screening: confirm if policy/programme needs GIA and define relevance. 2) Scoping: define affected groups + key gender/d&l questions; select indicators. 3) Data & evidence: gather sex-disaggregated + intersectional data; consult stakeholders. 4) Impact analysis: identify differential effects; map risks/benefits; consider alternatives. 5) Mitigation + redesign: adjust policy design, delivery and safeguards. 6) Monitoring plan: define indicators, baselines, and review schedule; publish GIA note. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Build a GIA template (2–4 pages) with mandatory fields: target population, pathways, affected services, data, risks. ▪ Use 'distributional tables': expected take-up/benefit by gender, age, disability, migration status. ▪ Run at least one stakeholder consultation step (CSOs + service users) and document responses. ▪ Require sign-off before approval gate (cabinet/council). 	<p>R — Policy owner (line department) completes GIA with support from GDEI unit.</p> <p>A — City executive/council committee approves policy only with completed GIA.</p> <p>C — Equality unit, data office, affected stakeholders.</p> <p>I — Decision-makers and public (publish summary).</p>	<p>Minimum: 2–3 weeks (light policy change; existing data).</p> <p>Standard: 4–8 weeks (consultation + analysis + redesign).</p> <p>Extended: 3–6 months (major infrastructure/urban plans with iterative redesign).</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ staff trained on GIA ▪ access to disaggregated data ▪ facilitation for consultation <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ analytic support (evaluation unit) ▪ qualitative research capability ▪ ability to commission studies 	<p>Inputs: % new policies screened; # staff trained on GIA.</p> <p>Outputs: % policies with completed GIA; % with mitigation measures adopted.</p> <p>Outcomes: reduction in gender gaps in service access/benefits (measured via Pillar 3 indicators).</p>
Pillar II — Policies	Gender Responsive Budgeting (GRB)	EIGE – Gender Budgeting	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Political commitment: GRB mandate + scope (whole budget or priority programmes). 2) Budget tagging: classify lines by gender relevance (direct / significant / neutral). 3) Gender needs assessment: analyse who benefits/pays; identify gaps. 4) Reallocation/design: adjust allocations and design of spending/revenues. 5) Performance framework: attach outputs/outcomes indicators and targets. 6) Budget cycle integration: annual reporting + audit trail; feed into next budget round. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create a tagging rulebook + short training for budget holders. ▪ Require each tagged line to specify: target group, expected reach, barriers, and planned mitigation. ▪ Use gender-disaggregated unit-cost and take-up data (e.g., childcare places, active labour programmes, health services). ▪ Publish a 'gender budget statement' annex to the city budget with the tagged lines and KPIs. 	<p>R — Budget office leads tagging and consolidates statement; line departments provide inputs.</p> <p>A — City executive and council approve budget with GRB annex.</p> <p>C — GDEI unit, service departments, data office, audit office.</p> <p>I — public and CSOs (consultation on priorities).</p>	<p>Minimum: pilot in 1–3 programmes within one budget cycle.</p> <p>Standard: 1 full budget cycle to tag + publish first statement.</p> <p>Extended: 2–3 cycles to refine tagging, add evaluation, and expand coverage.</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ budget analysts trained on GRB ▪ tagging taxonomy ▪ basic data on beneficiaries <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ performance budgeting infrastructure ▪ audit support ▪ capacity to evaluate programme impacts 	<p>Inputs: % of total budget tagged; # budget holders trained.</p> <p>Outputs: # tagged lines with KPIs; # reallocations justified by gender analysis.</p> <p>Outcomes: changes in gaps relevant to funded areas (e.g., childcare coverage; safety; health access).</p>

Pillar	Template	Template – where it comes from	Operational steps (strategic sequence + concrete outputs)	Tools	Roles & responsibilities (RACI: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed)	Suggested Timing	Required capacities (minimum viable + recommended)	KPIs (inputs → outputs → outcomes; plus disaggregation)
Pillar II — Policies	Gender-Responsive Procurement (GRPP)	EIGE – Gender-responsive public procurement World Bank – PPP Gender Toolkit: Mainstreaming gender in infrastructure OECD –Public procurement and gender equality	1) Procurement policy: adopt a GRPP policy statement and scope (which categories). 2) Market engagement: map suppliers and capacity; communicate expectations. 3) Tender design: include GDEI requirements in specifications/award criteria. 4) Contracting: embed KPIs and reporting clauses. 5) Contract management: monitor supplier performance; enforce remedies. 6) Learning loop: annual review of outcomes and update templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Create standard tender clauses: equal pay, anti-harassment policies, inclusive service delivery standards. ▪ Use weighted award criteria: e.g., supplier GDEI plan, workforce diversity, user-centred design. ▪ Require disaggregated service usage reporting (beneficiaries by gender/age/disability). ▪ Provide supplier guidance + capacity building (especially SMEs/social enterprises). 	R — Procurement unit embeds clauses and monitors contracts. A — Chief procurement officer/city manager ensures compliance. C — Legal, GDEI unit, service owner departments, supplier reps. I — audit office, public (summary contract KPI reporting).	Minimum: 1–2 months to create clause library + pilot tenders. Standard: 6–12 months to integrate into standard templates + train buyers. Extended: 18–24 months to build supplier ecosystem and full reporting.	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ procurement lawyers ▪ contract management capability ▪ KPI reporting template. <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ buyer training ▪ supplier engagement capacity ▪ data systems for contract KPIs 	<p>Inputs: % tenders using GRPP clauses; # procurement staff trained.</p> <p>Outputs: # contracts with gender KPIs; supplier compliance rates.</p> <p>Outcomes: improved service accessibility/safety for women and diverse groups; supplier workforce improvements.</p>
Pillar II — Policies	CO-CO-CO-CO (Co-design, Co-deployment, Co-management, Co-monitoring)		1) Co-design: diagnose needs and co-create solutions with target communities. 2) Co-deployment: implement pilots with community participation and shared decision rules. 3) Co-management: establish joint governance arrangements for ongoing operations. 4) Co-monitoring: co-define KPIs and collect feedback; iterate design.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Run 2-stage co-design workshop: (i) issue mapping + idea generation; (ii) participatory prototyping; then present prototypes to wider community for feedback. ▪ Use facilitation tools: graphic facilitation, collective mapping, participatory mock-ups (e.g., Lego), forum theatre. ▪ Accessibility: choose session times compatible with participants; provide translation/visual aids. ▪ Governance: agree a simple co-management charter (membership, decisions, conflict resolution, budget responsibility). ▪ Co-monitoring: create a 'community KPI board' (monthly check-ins) + digital feedback channel. 	R — Community engagement team/facilitator; project manager. A — Policy owner department (ultimately responsible for service delivery). C — Community reps, CSOs, neighbourhood committees; data office for monitoring; procurement if contracting. I — wider residents; elected officials (updates).	Minimum: 6–10 weeks (co-design + small pilot + initial monitoring). Standard: 3–6 months (co-deployment + governance set-up + KPI dashboard). Extended: 12 months (co-management stabilised + evaluation + scaling).	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ facilitation skills ▪ safeguarding protocols ▪ accessible engagement logistics <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ participatory design expertise ▪ community organising ▪ ability to fund participation (childcare, transport, translation) 	<p>Inputs: # participants engaged; diversity of participants; # engagement sessions.</p> <p>Outputs: # co-designed solutions/prototypes; governance charter agreed; # issues resolved through co-management.</p> <p>Outcomes: improved perceived safety/accessibility; sustained participation; reduced inequalities in service usage.</p>

Pillar	Template	Template – where it comes from	Operational steps (strategic sequence + concrete outputs)	Tools	Roles & responsibilities (RACI: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed)	Suggested Timing	Required capacities (minimum viable + recommended)	KPIs (inputs → outputs → outcomes; plus disaggregation)
Pillar II — Policies	Intersectional Impact Lens Integration Plan (IIL)	Government of Canada – GBA+ Action Plan 2019–21	<p>1) Governance & Capacity → Outputs: approved Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) Integration Framework; governance set-up; named Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) Champion; cross-sector network of ambassadors.</p> <p>2) Awareness & Training → Outputs: comms plan; training offer (incl. tailored sessions); tools repository.</p> <p>3) Integration & Impact → Outputs: mandatory Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) section embedded in key initiatives; review/challenge function; documented mitigations/changes.</p> <p>4) Data & Research → Outputs: disaggregated data strategy; targeted studies/analyses; evidence briefs.</p> <p>5) Monitoring & Reporting → Outputs: internal tracking system; periodic reports to senior management; external reporting on progress.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embed Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) into standard decision templates (policy notes, programme proposals, service design) with mandatory prompts: affected groups; barriers; disaggregated evidence; mitigation. Establish a review & challenge 'gate' before approval: the Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) GDEI support & review hub (central function) supports teams and checks quality. Build internal advisory capacity: create a cross-sector ambassador network; run office hours; maintain a tools library and examples. Training: targeted learning (basic + advanced) linked to real initiatives; communications to build awareness. Data: require disaggregated variables in core datasets; identify data gaps; run targeted research to surface hidden inequities. Monitoring: track where Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) was applied and document concrete ways it changed design/implementation; report internally and externally. 	<p>R — Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) GDEI support & review hub (central function) (0.75 FTE in example) – office of first responsibility: supports, habitates, tracks and monitors integration.</p> <p>A — Senior leadership committee / senior management – approves integration approach; monitors progress.</p> <p>C — Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) Champion (VP level) provides leadership; all policy / programme / service teams apply lens; data/analytics teams support evidence.</p> <p>I — Organisation-wide staff; external stakeholders via published progress reporting where applicable.</p>	<p>Minimum: 6–8 weeks to establish governance, update templates, and launch training.</p> <p>Standard: 12 months to embed review/challenge gate, build ambassador network, and create initial monitoring reports.</p> <p>Extended: multi-year maturity cycle (example action plan covers 2019–21).</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One central support function (GDEI support & review hub (central function)) + standard templates Basic staff training and communications <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disaggregated data capacity ('data-rich environment'), analytics and research capability Internal network of ambassadors to sustain integration Monitoring/reporting infrastructure to track concrete changes attributable to Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) 	<p>Inputs: # staff trained; training completion rate; # ambassadors appointed; capacity hours delivered.</p> <p>Outputs: % key initiatives/products with documented Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model); # reviews performed by GDEI support & review hub (central function); # guidance/tools produced, # documented mitigations/design changes resulting from Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model).</p> <p>Outcomes: Improved equity in access/experience of services/programmes (tracked via Pillar III indicators).</p> <p>Disaggregation: Track application by sector/department and by initiative type (policy / programme / service).</p>

Pillar 3

Diagnostic questions. If the answer is **no**, use the linked template(s) to address the gap.

[Go to Pillars' descriptions](#)

[Go to Pillar 1](#)

[Go to Pillar 2](#)

Pillar 3 — Table

Pillar	Template	Template – where it comes from	Operational steps (strategic sequence + concrete outputs)	Tools	Roles & responsibilities (RACI: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed)	Suggested Timing	Required capacities (minimum viable + recommended)	KPIs (inputs → outputs → outcomes; plus disaggregation)
Pillar III — Outcomes	Wellbeing Instruments (WHO-5, K6, etc.)		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select validated wellbeing instruments relevant to programme aims. 2) Define sampling frame (target communities + comparators) and ethics/GDPR. 3) Collect baseline + follow-ups; ensure consistent administration. 4) Score instruments, interpret clinically/meaningfully, and triangulate with qualitative feedback. 5) Report outcomes by subgroups; feed insights into redesign. 6) Repeat at set intervals to track change. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Standard operating procedure: same wording, same order, same mode of administration. ▪ Use short, low-burden tools in community settings; provide translation and accessibility formats. ▪ Combine with service-use data to explain mechanisms (e.g., participation in co-designed activities). ▪ Use pre-defined reporting templates (means, distributions, % above clinical thresholds, subgroup gaps). 	<p>R — Evaluation/data team administers tools and scores.</p> <p>A — Programme owner department signs off protocol.</p> <p>C — Community partners; ethics/GDPR officer; translators.</p> <p>I — participants and stakeholders (results feedback).</p>	<p>Minimum: baseline + 1 follow-up (8–12 weeks).</p> <p>Standard: baseline + 2 follow-ups (6–12 months).</p> <p>Extended: annual tracking over 2–3 years for institutional learning.</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ trained enumerators/facilitators ▪ scoring competence ▪ GDPR/ethics compliance <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ mixed-methods evaluation capability ▪ data linkage expertise ▪ partnerships with health researchers 	<p>Outcome KPIs: mean WHO-5 score; % with low wellbeing threshold; K6 distress distribution; subgroup gaps.</p> <p>Process KPIs: response rate, attrition, data completeness, translation coverage.</p>
Pillar III — Outcomes	Evaluation Designs	UK Magenta Book	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define evaluation question + theory of change. 2) Choose design: experimental, quasi-experimental, theory-based, mixed methods. 3) Define outcomes and data plan; ensure ethical and practical feasibility. 4) Implement data collection + analysis. 5) Report: effect estimates + uncertainty; process learning. 6) Embed learning into decision cycle (scale/stop/redesign). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Start from feasibility: what counterfactual is plausible (comparison group, before/after, matched areas). ▪ Use contribution analysis / process tracing when causal identification is not feasible. ▪ Document assumptions, threats to validity, and sensitivity analyses. ▪ Pre-specify analysis plan and data governance. ▪ Produce an 'evaluation one-pager' per intervention: design, data, timeline, and reporting outputs. 	<p>R — Evaluation lead (internal evaluation unit or external).</p> <p>A — Programme sponsor (department head) signs off evaluation plan.</p> <p>C — Data owners, service providers, community partners.</p> <p>I — decision-makers; public summary if appropriate.</p>	<p>Minimum: rapid evaluation (8–12 weeks) for pilots.</p> <p>Standard: 6–12 months for full cycle with follow-up.</p> <p>Extended: multi-year impact evaluation for structural programmes.</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ evaluation literacy ▪ ability to collect baseline and follow-up ▪ statistical support <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ dedicated evaluation unit ▪ mixed-methods expertise ▪ procurement to commission evaluators 	<p>Process KPIs: % interventions with evaluation plan; % with baseline; evaluation completion rate.</p> <p>Outcome KPIs: effect sizes on selected Pillar 3 outcomes and distributional impacts.</p>

Pillar	Template	Template – where it comes from	Operational steps (strategic sequence + concrete outputs)	Tools	Roles & responsibilities (RACI: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed)	Suggested Timing	Required capacities (minimum viable + recommended)	KPIs (inputs → outputs → outcomes; plus disaggregation)
Pillar III — Outcomes	Gender KPI Framework (indicator bank + KPI governance)	EIGE – Gender Statistics Database (DGS)	<p>1) Translate GDEI priorities into outcome domains (e.g., representation, safety, economic participation, access to services, time use, health/wellbeing) and define a results chain (inputs → outputs → outcomes).</p> <p>2) Select a minimum viable set of KPIs per domain from the EIGE DGS and document definitions, units of measure, disaggregation, sources, frequency, baseline and targets.</p> <p>3) Assign KPI owners and define data collection, validation and update routines; maintain a data gap register.</p> <p>4) Build internal dashboards and public summaries; link KPIs to review meetings and corrective actions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Indicator catalogue from EIGE DGS (definitions, disaggregation, sources, frequency). ▪ KPI register (spreadsheet) with metadata and governance fields. ▪ Data quality checklist, gap register and simple ETL notes. ▪ Dashboard (Excel/BI), review meeting template and corrective action log. 	<p>R — Statistics/data office or monitoring & evaluation unit (KPI register, data routines).</p> <p>A — City leadership / senior management (use of KPIs in decisions).</p> <p>C — Line departments (KPI owners), IT/data engineering, equality unit.</p> <p>I — Advisory councils, CSOs, communications teams and public (summary reporting).</p>	<p>Minimum: 1–2 months to define domains and set up KPI register. Standard: 3–6 months incl. dashboards and review routines. Extended: continuous, with annual revision of KPIs and targets.</p>	<p>Minimum viable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ access to administrative and survey data ▪ KPI register (Excel) ▪ basic dashboard tooling <p>Recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ indicator literacy ▪ data management and quality assurance capacity ▪ ability to translate trends into decisions 	<p>Inputs: share of selected KPIs with data; punctuality of updates; data quality flags resolved.</p> <p>Outputs: KPI register completed; dashboards produced; review meetings held.</p> <p>Outcomes: trend changes over time and reductions in outcome gaps between groups.</p>

GENDER DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION HANDBOOK

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Introduction

This handbook presents tools and strategies to implement Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion policies in cities based on the experience of the IN-HABIT Horizon 2020 project, which explores how small and medium-sized European cities can promote inclusive health and well-being. IN-HABIT was implemented in four cities—Córdoba (Spain), Riga (Latvia), Lucca (Italy), and Nitra (Slovakia)—each focusing on innovative dimensions such as culture and heritage, food, human–animal bonds, and art and environment to foster inclusivity. Central to the project is the recognition that health and well-being are common pool resources (CPRs) that must be co-created and managed collaboratively to ensure equitable access and sustainability.

The handbook builds on the Gendered Landscape (GL) framework, developed earlier in the project, which diagnoses and evaluates gender inequalities in urban contexts through three interconnected pillars: Institutions, Policies, and Outcomes. These pillars provide a practical structure for policymakers to mainstream gender and diversity considerations in urban planning and governance. For each pillar, a set of resources and recommendations derived from the literature are illustrated in practice by concrete actions implemented in each of the four IN-HABIT cities.

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1. Project Background

IN-HABIT is a Horizon 2020 research project on inclusive health and well-being in four small and medium size European cities funded by the European Commission. Each city aims to develop new solutions in four dimensions to foster inclusive health and well-being. More specifically, Cordoba (Spain) uses culture and heritage to promote inclusivity; Riga (Latvia) mobilises food to nurture daily healthier lifestyles; Lucca (Italy) promotes human-animal bonds as new relational urban good; Nitra (Slovakia) works with art and environment to connect places and people. Each city focuses its action on deprived areas and vulnerable groups such as children, elders, women, persons with disability, ethnic minorities and migrants.

A distinct approach of the programme has been to consider health and well-being as a common pool resource (CPR), created, managed and used by the community but affected by low excludability and high subtractability. Common pool resources are shared and available to everyone but are also scarce, with a finite supply. This makes them susceptible to exploitation and diminished availability if individuals pursue their own self-interest. Moreover, if individuals and groups' social interests are in conflict - for instance in cases in which they may have different willingness to cooperate and participate in the management of the resource - then there would clearly be incentives for users to ignore the social costs.

Viewing cities from a gender equality and diversity perspective requires understanding of the main differences affecting the use of the urban space. Acknowledging that different groups have different needs and experiences in the urban space is the first step towards more user-sensitive and inclusive public services, and ultimately more efficient ones.

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Therefore, integral to IN-HABIT is the development of a systemic urban planning framework based on innovative gender and diversity approaches. In order to establish this framework, INHABIT has developed, in a previous deliverable, a new methodology based on the idea of the Gendered Landscape. The concept of the Gendered Landscape is reflected in a comprehensive framework designed to help cities both diagnose existing gender inequalities and evaluate the effectiveness of policies that aim to reduce them. The motivation behind this framework comes from the recognition that cities are not neutral spaces; instead, they are shaped by historical, social, and political forces that often reflect and perpetuate gender inequalities.

The relationship between gender and urban spaces has a long history. Since the late 19th century, women’s movements advocated for a “municipal housekeeping” approach, arguing that cities should be planned with attention to social care, public health, and community well-being—functions traditionally linked to women’s roles. However, despite some progress in recent decades, cities have largely been designed and governed by male-dominated institutions, which means urban spaces often fail to accommodate the diverse needs of women and other marginalized groups.

Many studies show that women remain among the most vulnerable populations in urban areas. They face challenges related to mobility, safety, employment opportunities, and access to services, which are compounded by unpaid care work and social norms. Yet, paradoxically, women also play a crucial but often invisible role in sustaining the livability of cities.

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The Gendered Landscape approach, fully described in D6.2 of May 2022, was developed on the basis of a solid understanding of the relevant available literature and the practical experiences to-date, particularly an in-depth understanding of the mostly practitioners-based experiences, such as that of Vienna (Austria) and Umea (Sweden), but also feedback and discussions with key practitioners in URBACT Gender Equal Cities and exchange of ideas on similar initiatives in other clustering projects funded by the Horizon 2020 and other stakeholders. The aim is to allow the framework to reflect the specific local contexts; to identify key macro areas which could be applied across time and space and to be able to deliver practical tools for cities and stakeholders. The methodology for gendered landscapes is based on three pillars: one on **Institutional Landscape**, one on **Policies Landscape** and one on **Welfare outcomes Landscape**. This allows the gendered landscape to consider those dimensions that are key to gender mainstreaming overall but also those that are specific to the context of the cities in which the approach is operationalised.

For this reason, this report employs the same three pillars to provide a practical set of tools for policy makers in medium-sized cities; tools that can be deployed to ensure the effective consideration of GDEI into the planning, development and administration of cities. In fact, the focus on institutions, policies and outcomes offers an ideal and structured approach to the description of practical tools for policymakers who aim to establish and/or improve their organisation's planning from GDEI perspective.

The report is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces some definitions of concepts that are relevant to the consideration of GDEI in cities. Section 3 provides the bulk of the report by describing the set of tools. We present them within each of the three pillars of the Gendered Landscape framework. Therefore, for each of three sections, a brief summary of the pillar's key characteristics and aims is followed by two subsections on **how** and **what**. The former introduces the relevant tool and provides respective sources, resources and links to facilitate their implementation and use, while the latter summarises the various relevant initiatives of the INHABIT project in the four cities as they relate to the respective pillar.

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2. Gender Diversity and Inclusion in Cities - Definitions

This section introduces key concepts on the GDEI in cities. GDEI stands for Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion.

Gender refers to the meaning that a culture gives to biological differences ascribed to men and women at birth. Social construction (concept from sociology and anthropology) states that our identities are shaped through the inculcation of values into children from birth in the family, education systems, mass-media, etc. These are going to shape our behaviour and values along different dimensions of diversity, including class, ethnicity, age, gender, physical and mental ability, immigrant status, etc.

Identity relations are therefore different in different cultures, and they are not given by nature but socially constructed. Identity is not determined by biology, but by belonging to the social world, and the extent to which an identity is associated with negative perceptions has an important part in explaining the discrimination experienced by those who carry it.

Diversity refers to the range of different demographics and identities held by individuals and groups. It includes, but is not limited to, legally protected characteristics such as sex, gender, sexual orientation, race or ethnicity, nationality, age, health status, disability status, cultural background, political affiliation, religious affiliation, education type or level, socio-economic status, as well as other factors such as neurodiversity, lifestyle choices, personality types, and life experience.

Equity refers to the experience of fairness and justice achieved by the removal of barriers to opportunities and removal of discrimination. Achieving equity requires taking into account different needs and resources to achieve equal results. It also seeks to address historical and systemic inequalities to create conditions for everyone to have an equal chance to succeed. It is a means to equality.

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Equality refers to the notion that all human beings have the same value, implying that we all have the same fundamental human rights, should all receive the same level of respect and treatment with dignity, as well as all enjoying the same access to opportunities. It is the ultimate goal of equity.

Inclusion refers to an environment that is trusted by all to be respectful of differences and one that reduces inequities. Often referred to as belonging, inclusion refers to the attitudes, behaviours and practices that create that sense of belonging. It refers to a structured and intentional set of good practices

Intersectionality refers to the intersection and overlap of different aspects of a person's identity (e.g. those mentioned in the definition of diversity), creating compounded, unique and contextual experiences of privilege, discrimination, or oppression. It emphasizes the importance of understanding and addressing these overlapping and compounding effects

Discrimination is a situation in which individuals with identical productive characteristics are treated differently from each other on the basis of observable personal characteristics (such as age, ethnicity, gender, BMI, etc). This means that when discrimination occurs talent is systematically undervalued and both economic growth and innovation are hampered.

Stereotypes are cognitive shortcuts we use automatically to generate expectations of others' behaviour: we thus attach the expectation of what we think a group does to a person that comes from that group. Cerebral networks used to process self-identity (and connected to gender, ethnicity etc.) are different to those used to process more general knowledge and harder to change: correcting stereotypes with direct experience is difficult.

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Unconscious bias is the use of past learning that has never been challenged, that drives behaviour on the basis of past experience. Even though these biases have never been consciously noticed, they drive behaviour unconsciously which is why it is important to deal with them. They are better described as unconscious hypocrisy. Unconscious bias is different from bigotry or conscious prejudice where different groups of people are consciously judged negatively and these judgements are acted upon.

Shifting unconscious biases can be quite hard: we all have confirmation bias (we pay much greater attention to the information that confirms what we already believe than to new information), and we are also more likely to forget information that is contrary to our beliefs – belief bias.

A test which measures unconscious biases, the implicit association test (IAT): <https://implicit.harvard.edu/implicit/demo>.

Relevant external references

<https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/thesaurus/overview>

https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/151780/GNL_Guidelines_EN.pdf

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3. Toolkits for GDEI in policy making

The Gendered Landscape (GL) framework provides a structured way to understand and map gender inequalities in urban contexts. It consists of three interconnected pillars:

1. Institutional Landscape
2. Policies Landscape
3. Welfare outcomes Landscape

A fuller description and discussion of the GL approach is available in D.6.2 “*Gendered Landscape in the 4 IN-HABIT cities*” [<https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/D-6.2-Gendered-Landscapes-in-the-4-Cities.pdf>] and in “*Gendered Landscape: a framework for diagnosis and evaluation of gender inequalities in urban contexts*” (Della Giusta, Dubois & Razzu, 2024). Here, we employ this framework to introduce and discuss the key tools that can support policy-makers in establishing and developing a consistent approach to the integration of Gender Equality, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (GDEI) within urban governance and policy-making.

The GL approach, structured around the three pillars of institutions, policies and welfare outcomes, allows for a coherent and systematic organisation of both analytical and operational instruments. By explicitly distinguishing between institutional capacity, policy processes and welfare outcomes, the framework provides a clear logic for identifying where gender inequalities emerge, how they are reproduced, and through which levers they can be addressed. This structure also makes it possible to situate different policy tools within the pillar where they are most relevant and effective.

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Within IN-HABIT, the Gendered Landscape framework has been actively used to guide diagnosis, experimentation and implementation across the four pilot cities. Each pillar was operationalised through a combination of context-specific institutional arrangements, participatory practices and policy interventions, reflecting local conditions while addressing shared structural challenges related to inclusion, access and wellbeing. The project experience therefore provides a concrete empirical basis for identifying which types of tools are most relevant at each stage of the policy cycle and within each pillar of the framework.

Building on this experience, the sections that follow move beyond the conceptual description of the pillars and introduce a set of **operational templates** associated with each pillar. These templates systematise the lessons learned within IN-HABIT and translate the Gendered Landscape framework into **practical, implementable instruments** that policy-makers can use to operationalise GDEI considerations in day-to-day decision-making, policy design, implementation and evaluation.

The templates are not conceived as a single prescriptive model, but rather as a **modular and flexible toolbox**. They differ in scope, depth and level of institutional commitment required, and can therefore be selected, adapted and combined depending on the specific context, capacity and priorities of a city or public authority. Some templates are designed to support diagnosis and institutional readiness, others to guide policy formulation and implementation, and others to ensure monitoring, evaluation and learning on outcomes. This modularity allows policy-makers to adopt an incremental approach, starting from basic diagnostic or screening tools and progressively moving towards more advanced and integrated instruments as institutional capacity and data availability increase.

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The three sections that follow are structured in a similar way. First, each section provides a brief introduction to the relevant pillar of the Gendered Landscape. Second, it describes how IN-HABIT operationalised that pillar in practice across the pilot cities. Finally, it presents and discusses the key operational templates associated with the pillar, outlining their purpose, logic of intervention and conditions for use.

Taken together, this structure is intended to support policy-makers not only in understanding **what** tools are available, but also **why**, **when** and **how** different templates can be deployed as part of a coherent, evidence-based and context-sensitive GDEI strategy.

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3.1. Pillar I - Institutions

The aim of the Institutional Landscape pillar is to provide an exhaustive and structured mapping of the institutional, legal and governance frameworks that shape urban decision-making, in order to assess the extent to which Gender Equality, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (GDEI) considerations are effectively integrated. Each stage of the design and implementation of urban policies can generate unequal or discriminatory effects if institutional arrangements fail to recognise and address structural differences in needs, access and power. For this reason, policy-makers' commitment to inclusion is not only a political statement, but a core institutional condition for equitable urban transformation.

Publicly expressing support for inclusive policies is a necessary but insufficient condition for meaningful change. Credible institutional commitments require formal counterparts, such as legally binding objectives, transparent governance arrangements, dedicated resources, and mechanisms for accountability. The institutional landscape therefore encompasses both the formal and informal structures through which decisions are made, including laws and regulations, administrative departments, budgetary processes, coordination mechanisms, and participatory arrangements. In this context, fair representation and meaningful involvement of groups exposed to discrimination are essential to ensure that diverse needs and lived experiences are reflected in policy choices.

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Accordingly, this pillar examines how GDEI considerations are embedded within an organisation's key institutional governance structures, legal frameworks and decision-making processes. It asks whether there are explicit commitments to gender equality and diversity, whether adequate resources (such as dedicated budgets, staff and expertise) are allocated, and whether GDEI principles are integrated into both formal institutions (e.g. departments, offices and procedures) and informal governance networks. Particular attention is given to transparency, accountability and the use of evidence, as these elements are central to sustaining institutional change over time.

The institutional landscape is assessed along six key dimensions:

- i) Stakeholder Involvement: Inclusion of diverse groups, gender-balanced leadership, and mechanisms for citizen participation.
- ii) Political Commitment: Presence of gender equality strategies and gender-focused political roles within the organisation governance.
- iii) Legal Framework: Laws, regulations, and policies that embed gender equality in local governance.
- iv) Resources and Structures: Availability of budgets, dedicated offices, and trained personnel for gender issues.
- v) Accountability: Mechanisms such as gender audits, impact assessments, and gender budgeting that ensure policies are implemented effectively.
- vi) Data and Knowledge: Availability and use of gender-disaggregated data and evidence to inform policy-making.

Together, these dimensions provide a comprehensive picture of institutional readiness and capacity to address GDEI challenges in urban contexts.

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InHabit - related activities

Within IN-HABIT, the Institutional Landscape pillar was operationalised through a structured yet context-sensitive approach aimed at embedding Gender, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (GDEI) within institutional governance frameworks, decision-making processes and accountability mechanisms across the four pilot cities. The underlying assumption was that health outcomes and access to urban resources are deeply shaped by structural inequalities, and that addressing these inequalities requires institutional change rather than isolated or project-based actions.

The project therefore adopted an introspective perspective on institutional capacity, focusing on the formal and informal arrangements through which urban policies are designed, implemented and monitored. Rather than treating GDEI as an external normative objective, IN-HABIT sought to make visible how commitments to inclusion were translated—or failed to be translated—into legal frameworks, administrative routines, resource allocation, participation mechanisms and the use of evidence. This approach responded to a common challenge faced by cities: the risk that inclusive intentions remain symbolic if institutions lack the structures, resources and capabilities needed to sustain them over time.

To address this challenge, IN-HABIT implemented a systematic assessment of the institutional landscape, structured around six interrelated dimensions: stakeholder involvement, political commitment, legal framework, resources and structures, accountability mechanisms, and data and knowledge. These dimensions provided a comprehensive lens through which to evaluate institutional readiness for GDEI and to identify governance bottlenecks constraining effective implementation. Information was collected through a **dedicated institutional survey**, administered to key stakeholders and organisational units within each city. A draft version of this survey instrument is provided in **Annex 1**, enabling policy-makers to replicate the assessment process in other urban contexts.

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The data collected through the survey were subsequently used to construct **synthetic indicators** for each of the six dimensions. A detailed methodological guidance, provided in **Annex 2**, explains step by step how qualitative and quantitative responses can be transformed into comparable indices. These indices enable a summative assessment of institutional capacity and allow cities to benchmark their performance across dimensions and over time.

To support interpretation and strategic discussion, results can be represented through **visual tools** that summarise performance across the six dimensions in a single view. In particular, **Figure 1** provides an example of a **radar (spider) diagram** built from the survey-based indices collected in the IN-HABIT cities. The chart makes it possible to immediately identify which institutional dimensions are closest to an ideal configuration and which exhibit the largest gaps, thereby supporting prioritisation, internal reflection and communication with both decision-makers and stakeholders.

Building on this evidence base, policy-makers were able to use the results of the institutional assessment to conduct **SWOT analyses**, identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to GDEI within their governance systems. These analyses supported the prioritisation of institutional reforms and informed subsequent decisions regarding governance arrangements, participation strategies and the allocation of resources.

The institutional survey and index-based assessment were complemented by **systematic stakeholder mapping exercises**, which further strengthened transparency and accountability. Stakeholder mapping aimed to identify all actors involved in, or affected by, GDEI-related decisions within each project, community or city. An example of such a mapping is provided in **Annex 3** for the city of Córdoba. Stakeholders included municipal authorities, NGOs, civil society organisations, universities, educators, professionals and local residents. The mapping process followed principles of completeness and inclusiveness, ensuring that both institutional and community-level actors were considered, particularly those exposed to multiple forms of discrimination. By clarifying roles, relationships and available resources, stakeholder mapping

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supported the design of participatory governance arrangements and helped to identify gaps in representation.

While the analytical framework and tools were shared across cities, each pilot translated them into locally adapted institutional configurations. In **Córdoba**, the IN-HUB adopted a polycentric model of governance structured around three interconnected circles of actors—institutions, civil society and local communities—supported by extensive stakeholder mapping, door-to-door engagement and structured participatory processes. The IN-HUB was symbolically anchored through a dual launch at the University of Córdoba and in the Las Palmeras neighbourhood, reflecting its dual institutional and community orientation. Local Community Activators, recruited through open and inclusive procedures, played a crucial role as trusted intermediaries facilitating sustained engagement.

In **Riga**, institutional inclusion was strengthened through collaboration with KQ, a local social enterprise that leveraged established relationships with community members and municipal bodies. This partnership enabled engagement across neighbourhood, city and regional scales and supported a hybrid governance arrangement combining public ownership, private management and community activation of urban space. Continuous feedback mechanisms and jointly defined evaluation criteria allowed for adaptive management, ensuring that inclusivity remained central throughout implementation.

In **Lucca**, institutional introspection was pursued through a city-wide assessment of gender and diversity integration in policy-making. A GDEI-specific questionnaire, developed in collaboration with the councillor responsible for education and gender budgeting, was used to analyse political representation, budget allocations and accountability mechanisms. The IN-HUB established in January 2022 became an institutional anchor for inclusive co-design, supported by structured tools such as stakeholder mapping, engagement diaries and organisational charts, and facilitated closer collaboration across municipal departments.

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In **Nitra**, GDEI principles were institutionalised by embedding inclusive processes across all phases of the project. Stakeholder engagement involved municipal actors, technical experts, cultural practitioners and residents, with participatory workshops and events fostering trust and institutional legitimacy. Although some phases of implementation showed weaker links to perceived outcomes, the breadth and continuity of engagement ensured that GDEI values were reflected in institutional routines and governance practices.

Taken together, the IN-HABIT experience demonstrates that institutional change in support of GDEI requires both **structured diagnostic tools** and **sustained participatory engagement**. The combination of institutional surveys, index-based assessments, visual representations such as the radar diagram in Figure 1, stakeholder mapping and strategic analysis provided a robust foundation for identifying governance gaps and prioritising reforms. On this basis, the following section introduces a set of **operational templates** associated with the Institutional Landscape pillar, which systematise these experiences into transferable instruments to support diagnosis, governance reform and accountable institutional change in other urban contexts.

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Figure 1: Institutional Landscape in INHABIT

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3.1.1 Pillar I Instruments

Participatory Gender Audit

What is it? A structured, participatory organisational audit methodology that combines evidence review with staff and leadership engagement to diagnose formal and informal barriers to equality and inclusion. It is delivered through ready-to-use instruments (model questionnaire, staff survey, interview and focus-group guides) and produces a prioritised set of recommendations grounded in lived experience and organisational practice.

Problem it solves: Institutions can have policies ‘on paper’ while everyday practice remains unequal due to organisational culture, informal norms, or unreported barriers (e.g., harassment risks, exclusion from decision networks, unsafe working environments). A participatory audit solves this by revealing implementation-relevant constraints that standard compliance reviews and quantitative indicators typically miss—and by building ownership, which increases implementation success.

Operational steps and tools:

1. **Mandate and scope**

Secure the audit mandate and define objectives, agreeing on the audit scope at the institutional or unit level.

Tools: formal agreement on scope and objectives; reference to key audit standards.

2. **Team setup and evidence plan**

Establish the audit team and a reference group, and agree on the evidence collection strategy.

Tools: structured evidence pack including policies, HR data, recruitment and promotion stats, training logs, budget lines, and complaints mechanisms.

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3. Evidence collection

Gather information through document reviews, interviews, surveys, and focus groups.

Tools: interview guides mapped to thematic areas such as leadership commitment, culture, decision-making processes, and accountability.

4. Analysis and findings

Compare evidence against standards to identify gaps and good practices.

Tools: scoring framework to evaluate findings; cross-reference with evidence pack.

5. Validation and reporting

Validate findings with institutional stakeholders and finalize the audit report.

Tools: participation mechanism engaging mixed groups (staff, elected members, unions/associations) to co-interpret results; deliverable: scored audit report.

6. Action planning

Co-develop a follow-up action plan with clear responsibilities, deadlines, and monitoring arrangements.

Tools: action plan template including quick wins (0–3 months) and longer-term structural reforms (6–24 months).

Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: the whole organisation—leadership, managers, staff, and (where relevant) elected representatives. Key internal stakeholders: HR, ethics/ombudsperson or integrity office, occupational safety, staff representatives/unions, and department heads. External stakeholders: equality bodies or independent experts (for credibility), plus CSOs representing affected groups for contextual insights.

How to measure: response rates, and number and diversity of participants; number and severity of issues identified (policy/process/culture/safeguarding); number of recommendations and share converted into deliverable actions with owners and deadlines; staff perceptions of institutional commitment and climate (perceived inclusion, safety, fairness) and related HR outcomes (retention, promotion patterns).

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Resources: time for survey administration and facilitated sessions; a trained neutral facilitator or external audit expertise; access to internal HR/budget data and secure data handling for confidentiality including sensitive testimonies.

Capabilities: qualitative methods (interviews/focus groups), organisational diagnostics, safeguarding awareness, change-management skills, and an ability to track the action plan implementation.

Source (including templates and examples): OSCE/ODIHR – ‘Participatory Gender Audits’ (with annexed model questionnaire, model survey, and interview/focus group question guides).

GDEI Mainstreaming Architecture

What is it? An institutional ‘operating system’ for mainstreaming GDEI: formal mandates, a focal-point network, coordination and escalation routines, minimum requirements for proposals and services, capacity-building pathways, and accountability/reporting mechanisms. It specifies how GDEI becomes a routine requirement across departments rather than a specialist add-on.

Problem it solves: Mainstreaming fails when it relies on individual champions, when responsibilities are unclear, or when there are no standard checkpoints in everyday workflows. This template solves fragmentation and sustainability problems by hardwiring minimum GDEI requirements into governance and the policy/service production process—making implementation resilient to turnover and political cycles.

Operational steps and tools:

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1. Formal mandate and oversight

Establish a clear GDEI mandate through an approved strategy and a defined monitoring mechanism.

Tools: architecture map clarifying who owns the strategy, who conducts analysis (GIA/GRB), who manages data, and who reports.

2. Institutional structures

Set up the core governance arrangements, including a central GDEI unit and a network of gender focal points across line departments.

Tools: Terms of Reference for gender focal points specifying minimum time allocation (5–10%), training requirements, and reporting templates.

3. Accountability and reporting

Define the accountability chain, including reporting cycles, KPI ownership, and escalation routes.

Tools: hard-wired reporting arrangements (quarterly dashboard reviews, annual public report, and inputs into budget hearings).

4. Resourcing and capacity

Secure dedicated resources to deliver the mandate, including budget lines, staffing, and skills development.

Tools: capacity development plan covering baseline training and advanced modules (GIA, GRB, GRPP, data).

5. Integration into core processes

Embed GDEI responsibilities and checks into standard organisational processes, including the policy cycle, budget cycle, procurement, and HR.

Tools: checklist or self-assessment tool to identify and address weak links (e.g. unclear roles, input-only indicators).

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6. Transparency and continuous improvement

Make governance arrangements and progress visible and use feedback to strengthen the system over time.

Tools: published governance architecture diagram and annual progress report informed by monitoring and self-assessment.

Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: senior leadership, central GDEI unit, departmental focal points, and programme/service owners. Key internal stakeholders: HR (competencies, training), finance/budget (resource link), procurement, legal/compliance, monitoring/statistics, and IT/data teams. External stakeholders: representative groups consulted through standard participation mechanisms including other city council members, civil society advisory groups, and citizens.

How to measure: existence of strategy/mandate; number of focal points appointed and functionality of focal point network including training completion rates; % proposals/services meeting minimum requirements after GIA; % budget lines tagged; number of procurement tenders with gender clauses; quality scores from review gate; reporting punctuality; reduction in recurring gaps and policy blind spots flagged by audits/index over time and improved GDEI indicators.

Resources: central hub capacity (coordination + quality review) and leadership buy-in, focal points' allocated time, and training/tooling budget.

Capabilities: coordination, workflow design, facilitation, basic data literacy, and the ability to translate GDEI goals into operational requirements.

Source (including templates and examples): OECD – 'Toolkit for Mainstreaming and Implementing Gender Equality' (institutional mechanisms for mainstreaming), complemented by EIGE mainstreaming toolkits.

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GDEI Action Plan — institutional transformation plan

What is it? A full-cycle institutional transformation plan structured around a recurring cycle: assessment → plan and adoption → implementation and monitoring → evaluation and renewal. It standardises how an organisation sustains GDEI progress across time, ensuring accountability, learning and continuity.

Problem it solves: One-off initiatives rarely change structures or culture, and progress often stalls when leadership changes or attention shifts. This template solves the continuity problem by requiring an evidence-based baseline, a cost set of owned measures, a monitoring routine, and a formal evaluation that feeds the next cycle.

Operational steps and tools:

1. Institutional diagnosis

Conduct a GDEI institutional assessment using surveys and/or a participatory audit to establish a baseline and identify strengths and gaps.

Tools: institutional survey results and participatory audit evidence.

2. Prioritisation of reforms

Translate diagnostic findings into a ranked backlog of institutional reforms across governance, HR, budgeting and procurement, and data systems.

Tools: structured synthesis of diagnostic inputs to support prioritisation.

3. GDEI Action Plan (GEAP) development

Develop and formally adopt a GDEI Action Plan defining objectives, measures, owners, timelines, resources, and KPIs.

Tools: GDEI Action Plan template (one measure per line: problem, action, owner, budget, timeline, KPI).

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4. Implementation and delivery

Implement reforms through a detailed Institutional Action Plan with clear ownership, milestones, deliverables, and tracking arrangements.

Tools: Institutional Action Plan and monitoring log (milestones, status, dependencies).

5. Monitoring and reporting

Track implementation progress and results through regular reviews and KPI monitoring.

Tools: reporting templates, including an internal dashboard and a public-facing summary.

6. Evaluation and learning

Conduct GDEI-responsive evaluations to assess effectiveness and inform adjustments, scaling, or redesign of measures.

Tools: evaluation criteria and a learning loop feeding into the next GEAP planning cycle.

Targets and stakeholders: Primary Targets: the entire organization, senior leadership. Key internal stakeholders: HR, finance/budget, procurement, legal/compliance, data/M&E, IT/data governance, staff representatives.

How to measure: implementation rate of measures; reporting compliance; changes in institutional readiness indicators; improvements in representation/pay/training and staff climate; evidence of policy/service improvements linked to institutional reforms.

Resources: leadership commitment, time for assessment/consultation, budget for capacity-building and process changes, and a monitoring routine.

Capabilities: organisational diagnostics, change management, basic monitoring & evaluation, and clear internal communication.

Source (including templates and examples): EIGE – ‘Gender Equality Action Plans’ (4-step cycle, monitoring and evaluation checklists), OSCE/OECD action-planning practice (turning audit/diagnostic findings into deliverables).

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3.2. Pillar II - Policies

This pillar evaluates whether the city's specific policies reflect gender-sensitive planning. It covers various sectors, including (but not limited to):

- Transportation
- Public safety
- Housing
- Public spaces and parks
- Education and employment
- Healthcare

A critical aspect here is whether cities use co-design processes involving women and underrepresented groups in developing solutions. This pillar focuses on policies from two perspectives. On one hand it aims to map, from a gender lens, the policies of the city in specific areas, such as those above. The goal is to determine whether cities are not only adopting gender-equality policies but also embedding gender perspectives throughout the entire policy cycle—from planning to implementation and evaluation. An important aspect of this will be information on the policy process and the extent to which this incorporates the key gendered experiences in the urban space under consideration, for instance by adopting co-design approaches and involving key stakeholders. On the other hand, this pillar aims to use the mapping of existing policies and principles - which, in certain circumstances, can be considered as providing a baseline - in order to understand how to evaluate and, therefore, design policies from a gender perspective both in relation to their outcomes and in relation to the extent to which the policies themselves are designed in an inclusive manner. An important step is certainly to fully evaluate the impact of interventions, which is often a missing element in consideration of gender equality in many contexts.

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InHabit Related Activities

Within IN-HABIT, the Policies pillar was operationalised as a **policy experimentation and learning instrument**, aimed at embedding GDEI considerations into concrete policy choices through participatory design, iterative implementation and evidence-informed evaluation. The project treated policies not as static instruments, but as evolving processes shaped by interaction between institutions, communities and urban space.

The rationale for this approach was the recognition that top-down policy solutions often fail to capture lived realities, particularly those of women and groups exposed to intersecting forms of disadvantage. Without structured engagement and feedback, policies risk reproducing exclusion even when motivated by inclusive intentions. IN-HABIT therefore focused on strengthening policy awareness, design quality and responsiveness by integrating participation, reflection on stereotypes and bias, and systematic assessment of impacts throughout the policy cycle.

Operationally, this was achieved through a sequence of interrelated steps. First, policy design was grounded in **co-creation processes** involving residents and stakeholders directly affected by the interventions. Through participatory workshops, focus groups, surveys, storytelling and action-research methods, policy problems and priorities were defined in close connection with everyday experiences. These processes helped surface gendered patterns of use, access and safety that would otherwise remain invisible in conventional planning approaches.

Second, policies were developed and tested through **iterative implementation**, combining soft and hard interventions and allowing for adaptation based on real-time feedback. Rather than finalising policy designs ex ante, IN-HABIT emphasised piloting, learning and adjustment, ensuring that measures remained responsive to diverse needs and evolving conditions.

Third, policy implementation was accompanied by **structured monitoring and evaluation**, using both qualitative and quantitative data. Disaggregated data, user feedback and

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observational tools were employed to assess who benefited from interventions, how access and use changed over time, and whether unintended effects emerged. This evidence was used not only to assess outcomes, but also to inform adjustments in policy design and delivery.

A range of practical tools supported these steps, including participatory diagnostics, stakeholder engagement formats, surveys, engagement diaries, feedback mechanisms, and simple evaluation instruments tailored to local contexts. Training activities addressing stereotypes and unconscious bias were also used to strengthen policy-makers' awareness and to support behaviour change within administrations. Responsibility for these processes typically involved close collaboration between policy departments, engagement teams, local partners and community actors, with coordination roles often anchored in IN-HUB structures.

Across the four pilot cities, this approach translated into locally adapted policy practices.

In **Córdoba**, policy development was grounded in Participatory Action Research, which informed the design of over twenty soft Visionary and Integrated Solutions addressing gender, culture, youth inclusion, digital literacy and environmental health. The flagship intervention—the renaturalisation of Las Palmeras—was co-designed with residents and assessed through longitudinal surveys, observational tools and media tracking. The emergence of the Las Palmeras Committee as a multi-actor governance structure exemplified how participatory policy processes can evolve into sustained community-led policy stewardship.

In **Riga**, policies prioritised multifunctionality, accessibility and age-friendly design through the transformation of the Āgenskalns market. Co-design workshops and participatory decision-making shaped interventions such as improved walkability, lift installation and dedicated zones for older residents. Continuous feedback and targeted measures helped address exclusion risks and manage gentrification pressures, demonstrating policy adaptation in response to social dynamics.

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In **Lucca**, policy work combined a gendered landscape approach with targeted inclusivity assessments. Surveys, focus groups and storytelling identified barriers to visibility and access, informing tailored outreach and policy adjustments. GDEI guidelines were applied across local activities, from training Local Community Activators to developing Inclusive Health and Wellbeing indicators. Policy coordination was supported by thematic working groups and practical tools such as engagement diaries and shared calendars.

In **Nitra**, policies were shaped through a strong intersectional lens, addressing overlapping vulnerabilities related to gender, age, disability, migration status and ethnicity. Co-creation processes guided inclusive spatial planning interventions, such as those implemented in Hidepark and along the cyclotraffic corridor. Data disaggregation and feedback loops enabled differentiated impact assessment and adaptive responses, including adjustments prompted by the arrival of Ukrainian refugees.

Taken together, the IN-HABIT experience demonstrates that embedding GDEI into urban policies requires treating policy-making as a participatory, iterative and evaluative process. By combining co-creation, adaptive implementation and evidence-informed learning, the project operationalised gender-sensitive planning across diverse policy domains. These experiences provide the empirical foundation for the operational policy templates introduced in the following section, which formalise and systematise these approaches into transferable instruments for broader application.

3.2.1 Pillar II Instruments

Gender Impact Assessment (GIA)

What is it? A structured ex-ante assessment tool that examines how a proposed policy, programme or service may affect different population groups and how to mitigate unequal

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impacts. It produces a concise, evidence-based ‘impact note’ that becomes part of the decision file and improves design choices before implementation.

Problem it solves: Many interventions appear neutral but generate unequal effects because baseline conditions differ by gender and intersecting characteristics (age, disability, migration status, income, caring responsibilities). GIA solves the ‘unintentional bias by design’ problem by making distributional impacts visible early and forcing mitigation measures and monitoring indicators to be specified before approval.

Operational steps and tools:

1. Screening

Determine whether a policy or programme requires a GIA and confirm its relevance and proportionality.

Tools: GIA template with mandatory screening fields to document scope and applicability.

2. Scoping

Identify affected groups, define key gender and diversity questions, and select relevant indicators.

Tools: GIA template sections covering target population, impact pathways, affected services, and indicators.

3. Data and evidence

Collect sex-disaggregated and intersectional data and incorporate qualitative evidence from stakeholders.

Tools: distributional tables showing expected take-up or benefits by gender, age, disability, and migration status, and at least one documented stakeholder consultation with CSOs and service users.

4. Impact analysis

Assess differential effects across groups, map risks and benefits, and consider

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alternative design options.

Tools: structured analysis within the GIA template supported by distributional evidence.

5. **Mitigation and redesign**

Adjust policy design, delivery mechanisms, and safeguards to address identified risks and inequities.

Tools: documented mitigation measures and design changes captured in the GIA template.

6. **Monitoring and approval**

Define indicators, baselines, and a review schedule, and ensure accountability before final approval.

Tools: published GIA note and mandatory sign-off at the approval gate (cabinet or council).

Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: policy teams, service designers, programme managers and decision-makers preparing proposals. Key internal stakeholders: central GDEI hub and departmental focal points (quality review), statistics/data unit, legal, finance (where costs/benefits change), and engagement teams. External stakeholders: affected groups of citizens (through consultations) to validate assumptions and mitigate blind spots.

How to measure: % new policies screened; % policies with completed GIA; % policies with mitigation measures adopted; average time-to-complete; number of design changes recorded; number of staff trained on GIA; downstream access/uptake and outcome gaps by group.

Resources: a standard GIA template (checklist + form), access to disaggregated data, a review mechanism, and time for targeted engagement.

Capabilities: basic impact reasoning, data literacy, and facilitation of stakeholder inputs; a central team able to coach and challenge low-quality GIAs.

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Source (including templates and examples): EIGE – ‘Gender Impact Assessment’ (Gender Mainstreaming Toolkit).

Gender Responsive Budgeting (GRB)

What is it? A method to integrate GDEI objectives into the full budget cycle by analysing how resources are allocated and who benefits, then adjusting budgets to address inequalities. Operationally, it relies on practical instruments (budget tagging, tracking tables, checklists and reporting formats) that make spending transparent from a GDEI perspective.

Problem it solves: Budgets are where policies become real. Without GRB, equality commitments remain rhetorical and spending can unintentionally widen gaps (e.g., underfunding care access, safety, mobility, or targeted inclusion services). GRB solves the ‘resource accountability’ problem by linking allocations and execution to distributional effects and outcome indicators.

Operational steps and tools:

1. **Political commitment**

Establish a formal GRB mandate and define its scope, covering either the whole budget or selected priority programmes.

Tools: governance decision setting the mandate and expectations for gender tagging and reporting.

2. **Budget tagging**

Classify budget lines by their gender relevance (direct, significant, neutral) to make gender impacts visible across spending and revenues.

Tools: a tagging rulebook supported by short, targeted training for budget holders.

3. **Gender needs assessment**

Assess who benefits from and who pays for budget measures, and identify gaps or

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unintended impacts.

Tools: requirement for each tagged line to specify target groups, expected reach, key barriers, and planned mitigation measures.

4. **Reallocation and programme design**

Adjust budget allocations and programme design to address identified gender gaps and improve equity.

Tools: use of gender-disaggregated unit-cost and take-up data (e.g. childcare places, labour market programmes, health services) to inform choices.

5. **Performance framework**

Link budget measures to clear outputs, outcomes, and targets to track results.

Tools: KPIs derived from tagged budget lines and associated data sources.

6. **Budget cycle integration**

Embed GRB into the annual budget process through reporting, transparency, and accountability, and use results to inform the next budget round.

Tools: publication of a gender budget statement annex to the city budget, including tagged lines and KPIs, supported by an audit trail.

Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: finance/budget office and policy departments responsible for programmes. Key internal stakeholders: senior leadership (approval), central GDEI unit (method support/quality), service owners (beneficiary data), procurement (where spending flows through contracts), and auditors/oversight bodies.

How to measure: number and share of budget lines tagged/analysed; number of budget holders trained; completeness of beneficiary profiling; number/value of reallocations justified by GRB; changes in service uptake by group; progress on targeted outcome indicators.

Resources: access to budget and programme data, a tagging taxonomy, an annual reporting slot, and light analytical support.

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Capabilities: public finance literacy (including GRB and tagging taxonomy), basic distributional analysis, performance management, and the ability to connect spending to beneficiaries and outcomes.

Source (including templates and examples): EIGE – ‘Gender budgeting in the ESIFs: Practical tools and Member State examples’ (and broader EIGE gender budgeting guidance).

Gender-Responsive Public Procurement (GRPP)

What is it? A procurement approach that embeds GDEI objectives into tender design, supplier selection, contract clauses and performance monitoring. It converts equality priorities into enforceable requirements and measurable KPIs within the commissioning and contract-management process.

Problem it solves: Procurement is a major municipal lever. Without GRPP, public contracts can exclude women-owned businesses, overlook accessibility and safety needs, and fail to prevent harassment/GBV risks during delivery. GRPP solves the ‘implementation through spending’ problem by using contracts as a delivery mechanism for inclusion, not only as a purchasing function.

Operational steps and tools

1. Procurement policy

Adopt a GRPP policy statement and define its scope by identifying priority procurement categories. Set expectations on GDEI objectives and signal forthcoming requirements to the market.

Tools: supplier guidance materials outlining GRPP principles and expectations.

2. Market engagement

Map supplier markets and assess capacity, with particular attention to SMEs and social

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enterprises, and communicate GDEI and GRPP expectations early.

Tools: supplier guidance and targeted capacity-building support.

3. **Tender design**

Integrate GDEI requirements into tender documentation and evaluation frameworks.

Tools: standard tender clauses (equal pay, anti-harassment, inclusive service delivery standards) and weighted award criteria (e.g. supplier GDEI plan, workforce diversity, user-centred design).

4. **Contracting**

Formalize GDEI commitments through enforceable contractual provisions.

Tools: contractual KPIs and clauses requiring disaggregated service usage reporting (by gender, age, disability).

5. **Contract management**

Monitor supplier performance against contractual GDEI requirements and apply remedies where commitments are not met.

Tools: review of KPI performance and analysis of disaggregated reporting data.

6. **Learning loop**

Conduct an annual review of outcomes to assess impact, capture lessons learned, and update policy scope, clauses, criteria, and guidance.

Tools: consolidated analysis of monitoring data and feedback from suppliers and service users.

Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: procurement office, contract managers and commissioning departments. Key internal stakeholders: legal (clauses), finance (value-for-money/performance), central GDEI unit (review), service delivery teams, suppliers, and users/community groups providing feedback.

How to measure: % tenders using GRPP clauses; number of staff trained; % contracts with GDEI clauses/KPIs; supplier compliance rates; supplier diversity metrics; supplier workforce improvements; grievance volume and resolution time; user satisfaction gaps by group.

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Resources: procurement templates, clause/KPI library, monitoring capacity, and a clear governance gate for sensitive categories.

Capabilities: procurement and contract management expertise plus GDEI/safeguarding know-how to translate objectives into measurable requirements.

Source (including templates and examples): EIGE mainstreaming toolkit components relevant to procurement, complemented where needed by operational contracting toolkits from the World Bank PPP Gender Toolkit.

Intersectional Impact Lens Integration Plan (GBA+ model)

What is it? An organisational embedding plan for an intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model). It operationalises consistent use by specifying governance, training, mandatory template fields, a review/challenge gate, data improvements, and monitoring/reporting routines.

Problem it solves: Even when assessment tools exist, they are applied inconsistently across departments. This template solves ‘implementation drift’ by integrating the lens into routine workflows and accountability structures, so that analysis happens systematically—not only when motivated individuals push for it.

Operational steps and tools

1. Governance & Capacity

Establish the governance and operating model for the Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model), including formal approval of the Integration Framework, designation of a Champion, and creation of a cross-sector ambassador network.

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Tools available: build internal advisory capacity through an ambassador network, office hours, and a shared tools library with practical examples.

2. **Awareness & Training**

Build organizational understanding and skills to apply the Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) consistently.

Tools available: targeted training (basic and advanced) linked to real initiatives, supported by a communications plan to raise awareness.

3. **Integration & Impact**

Systematically embed the Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model) into decision-making and project design, and ensure quality control before approval.

Tools available: embed mandatory prompts in standard decision templates (policy notes, programme proposals, service design) and establish a review and challenge gate through a central GDEI support and review hub.

4. **Data & Research**

Strengthen the evidence base to inform intersectional analysis and decision-making.

Tools available: require disaggregated variables in core datasets, identify data gaps, and commission targeted research and analyses to surface hidden inequities.

5. **Monitoring & Reporting**

Track application, outcomes, and influence of the Intersectional impact lens (GBA+ model), and ensure accountability.

Tools available: monitoring systems that record where the lens was applied and how it changed design or implementation, combined with periodic internal reporting and external progress reporting.

Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: policy/service teams and decision-makers; central GDEI hub responsible for enabling and quality assurance. Key stakeholders: statistics/data

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units, HR/training, engagement teams, legal, and external groups consulted to validate impacts and assumptions.

How to measure: % proposals with completed impact-lens section; number of reviews performed; documented design changes; training coverage (number of trainees, completion rate, capacity hours delivered); number of ambassadors appointed; improvements in data availability and quality; number of guidance/tools produced. All outcomes disaggregated by sector/department and by initiative type whenever possible.

Resources: small central function and internal network; minimal budget for training and analytics; stable decision templates.

Capabilities: workflow design, coaching/review skills, data literacy, and the ability to document and learn from changes prompted by analysis.

Source (including templates and examples): Canada – ‘GBA+ Action Plan 2019–21’ (organisational embedding model for an intersectional impact lens).

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3.3. Pillar III - Outcomes

The third pillar focuses on measuring gender inequalities in outcomes that directly affect people's well-being. It goes beyond policy intentions to assess actual results, looking at a range of possible wellbeing outcomes that are relevant to the specific context, programme, project. It aims to provide an answer to the key question on what the ultimate outcomes that the project, programme or activity wants to achieve. These could include:

- Economic well-being
- Health outcomes
- Educational attainment
- Safety and perceptions of safety
- Access to services and public spaces
- Subjective well-being (life satisfaction, mental health, happiness)

InHabit Related Activities

Within IN-HABIT, the Welfare Outcomes pillar was implemented as an operational evaluation approach to Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW), combining structured quantitative instruments with participatory and creative methods to capture change among vulnerable and underrepresented groups. Outcomes were assessed across five interconnected dimensions of IHW: subjective wellbeing, spatial and environmental wellbeing, social wellbeing, economic wellbeing, and healthy lifestyles. The rationale was that conventional metrics alone often fail to reflect the complexity of lived experience and the differentiated effects of urban interventions across groups, particularly in structurally disadvantaged contexts. IN-HABIT therefore treated outcome measurement not as a purely technical task, but as a mixed-methods system designed to make distributional impacts visible, support learning during implementation, and enable accountability at the end of interventions.

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In practice, the project combined validated wellbeing scales with locally adapted tools. Quantitative measurement included psychological wellbeing instruments such as the WHO-5 Well-Being Index and the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K6), used to assess differences in subjective wellbeing and mental health across participants and groups. These measures were complemented by qualitative approaches such as focus groups, storytelling and observational tools, which allowed participants to articulate experiences often excluded from standard indicators (including perceptions of safety, belonging, trust, exclusion and everyday constraints). Where relevant, data were collected and analysed with attention to intersectionality, enabling differentiated assessment by gender, ethnicity, disability and socio-economic status.

A distinctive operational component of IN-HABIT's outcomes work was the use of behavioural and collective-action tools to measure cooperation, trust and willingness to contribute to common resources. Annex 4 (Behavioural Games Handbook for cities) provides practical guidance on the implementation of common pool resource games and related behavioural games, which can be used to elicit preferences, identify behavioural constraints (such as present bias), assess social norms and trust, and test solutions that promote cooperative behaviour. These tools are particularly useful at neighbourhood or municipal scale, where interventions often aim to strengthen collective stewardship, social cohesion and sustained use of shared spaces.

The evaluation approach also relied on clear roles and capacities. Implementation required coordination between municipal teams and project partners responsible for monitoring and evaluation, as well as engagement teams and community actors who facilitated inclusive data collection and interpretation. Local intermediaries (including trusted facilitators and community activators) were particularly important for reaching groups exposed to discrimination and for ensuring that measurement tools were accessible and ethically administered. Resources needed included basic data collection capability, skills in administering standardised scales, and an agreed workflow for data management, disaggregation and reporting.

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Across the pilot cities, IN-HABIT applied this outcomes logic in locally adapted ways. In Córdoba, the combination of longitudinal surveys and community-led data collection supported measurement of changes in perceptions of safety, spatial justice and psychological wellbeing. Participatory tools, including storytelling and gamified instruments, enabled groups such as Roma residents, LGBTIQ+ individuals, women survivors of gender-based violence and children in marginalised neighbourhoods to articulate lived experiences often absent from traditional metrics. The integration of soft and hard interventions was reflected in visible behavioural and social outcomes, including increased use of public space and reduced vandalism, alongside strengthened community stewardship.

In Riga, the transformation of the multifunctional market was assessed as an outcome pathway towards social cohesion and collective identity. Monitoring combined statistical and sociological methods, supported by qualitative feedback such as focus groups, to trace changes in social capital, belonging and engagement. Participants described the market as a community anchor, highlighting the value of mixed-method evaluation for capturing nuanced effects, particularly for groups at risk of economic exclusion.

In Lucca, outcome evaluation combined intersectional wellbeing measures with tools sensitive to safety, inclusion and access in public space. The project documented both high participation of women and Roma residents in specific activities and persistent barriers in reaching other marginalised groups, explicitly identifying these gaps as priorities for future action. Qualitative tools, including storytelling interviews and baseline assessments, supported the identification of changes in perceived inclusion, leisure access and wellbeing linked to the One Health and human–animal bond approaches.

In Nitra, outcomes assessment emphasised differentiated impacts across a wide range of vulnerable groups, including migrants, persons with disabilities, LGBTQI+ individuals, older residents and people living alone. Participation in co-design activities was strongly associated with perceived benefits, especially in social wellbeing. At the same time, the project identified

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equity gaps—particularly for Roma communities and older populations—highlighting the need for more tailored outcome measurement and targeted policy responses. A Social Return on Investment analysis supported the conclusion that interventions generated substantial social value, reinforcing the case for inclusive urban innovation.

Taken together, the IN-HABIT experience demonstrates that GDEI-sensitive outcomes are not only measurable but can be captured in a way that respects complexity, intersectionality and local agency. By integrating validated wellbeing instruments, disaggregated data practices, behavioural tools (including those described in Annex 4), and mixed-method evaluation designs, the project operationalised a welfare outcomes approach that supports learning during implementation and accountability for results. On this basis, the following section introduces operational templates associated with the Welfare Outcomes pillar, designed to systematise these practices into transferable tools for monitoring, evaluation and outcomes-based GDEI decision-making.

3.3.1 Pillar III Instruments

Gender KPI Framework

What is it? A practical ‘KPI system’ for outcomes monitoring, built by selecting, defining and governing a coherent set of gender-related indicators from an official reference bank (EIGE DGS). It combines (i) an indicator catalogue (definitions, disaggregation, sources, frequency) with (ii) governance rules (who owns each KPI, how it is updated, how it is used in decisions).

Problem it solves: Cities often measure activities (number of workshops, number of participants) rather than outcomes (changes in access, safety, wellbeing, representation, time use). A KPI framework solves the ‘measurement fragmentation’ problem by standardising

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indicator definitions and turning monitoring into a repeatable system that can be audited, communicated and used to steer policy.

Operational steps and tools:

1. Define outcome domains and results chain

Translate GDEI priorities into a clear set of outcome domains (e.g. representation, safety, economic participation, access to services, time use, health and wellbeing) and articulate a results chain linking inputs, outputs, and outcomes.

Tools: EIGE DGS indicator catalogue to inform domain selection and alignment with recognized definitions.

2. Select and specify KPIs

Identify a minimum viable set of KPIs for each outcome domain and document their technical specifications.

Tools: EIGE DGS indicator catalogue (definitions, disaggregation, sources, frequency) and a KPI register (spreadsheet) capturing units of measure, baselines, targets, and governance metadata.

3. Set up data governance and collection

Assign KPI owners and define data collection, validation, and update routines, while actively tracking limitations.

Tools: data quality checklist, data gap register, and simple ETL notes to document data flows and constraints.

4. Monitor, review, and act

Develop internal dashboards and public summaries, and integrate KPI review into management processes with clear follow-up actions.

Tools: dashboard (Excel or BI), review meeting template, and corrective action log to support decision-making and accountability.

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Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: city leadership and departments responsible for service delivery and policy outcomes. Key stakeholders: statistics/data office, monitoring & evaluation unit, IT/data engineering (where present), and departmental KPI owners (service heads). External stakeholders: equality bodies, advisory councils and CSOs can be consulted on indicator relevance and interpretation; communications teams support public reporting.

How to measure: KPI coverage (share of selected KPIs with data), punctuality of updates, data quality flags resolved, trend changes over time, and reductions in outcome gaps between groups.

Resources: access to administrative and survey data, a KPI register, dashboard tooling (Excel is enough for MVP), and governance time for review meetings.

Capabilities: indicator literacy, data management, quality assurance, and the ability to translate trends into decisions (performance management).

Source (including templates and examples): EIGE – Gender Statistics Database (DGS) + EIGE guidance on gender indicators (used as the reference bank for KPI definitions).

Evaluation Designs (method selection + evaluation planning)

What is it? A structured menu and decision logic for choosing evaluation designs and analytical methods that fit the policy question, available data, constraints and required credibility. It supports a proportionate approach—ranging from process evaluation and theory-based evaluation to quasi-experimental impact designs and economic evaluation.

Problem it solves: Cities often confuse monitoring with evaluation and rely on weak before/after narratives that are not credible for accountability or learning. This template solves

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the ‘method mismatch’ problem by helping teams pick feasible designs that can credibly answer the question, and by clarifying what data must be collected upfront.

Operational steps and tools:

1. **Frame the evaluation**

Define the evaluation question and theory of change, grounded in what can realistically be tested.

Tools: assess feasibility upfront by identifying a plausible counterfactual (comparison group, before/after, matched areas).

2. **Select the evaluation design**

Choose an appropriate design—experimental, quasi-experimental, theory-based, or mixed methods—based on feasibility and decision needs.

Tools: apply contribution analysis or process tracing where causal identification is not feasible.

3. **Plan outcomes, data, and governance**

Specify outcomes, indicators, data sources, and ethical considerations, and ensure practical feasibility.

Tools: pre-specify the analysis plan and data governance arrangements; document key assumptions.

4. **Implement and analyse**

Carry out data collection and analysis in line with the agreed design and plan.

Tools: document threats to validity and conduct sensitivity analyses where relevant.

5. **Report results and learning**

Communicate findings clearly, including effect estimates, uncertainty, and process insights.

Tools: produce a concise evaluation one-pager per intervention summarizing design, data, timeline, and outputs.

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6. Embed learning in decisions

Feed evaluation results into the decision cycle to inform scaling, redesign, or discontinuation of interventions.

Tools: use the documented findings and assumptions to support evidence-based decisions.

Targets and stakeholders: Primary targets: monitoring & evaluation staff, programme owners, and leadership approving evaluation plans. Key stakeholders: data owners, procurement (if commissioning evaluators), legal/ethics, and community stakeholders for qualitative components.

How to measure: % interventions with evaluation plan; % with baseline, evaluation completion rate; quality of evaluation plans (design appropriateness), delivery against timeline, transparency of limitations, and documented use of findings (decisions taken/changed); effect sizes on Pillar 3 outcomes and distributional impacts.

Resources: evaluation expertise (internal/external), access to data, time for baseline collection, and governance for commissioning.

Capabilities: evaluation literacy, data governance, analytical skills proportionate to chosen design, and clear reporting.

Source (including templates and examples): HM Treasury / UK Government – Magenta Book (Annex A: analytical methods for evaluation).

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4. List of resources for cities

Name Organization	Website link	Policy domain focus	Type of reso urce	Relevance for city policy-makers
European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) – Gender Statistics Database	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs	Data monitoring across 14 policy areas	Data port al	Benchmark local gaps, build indicators for municipal strategies and reporting.
OECD – Toolkit for Mainstreaming and Implementing Gender Equality (2023)	https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/toolkit-for-mainstreaming-and-implementing-gender-equality-2023_3ddef555-en.html	Governance, budgeting, procurement, HR	Tool kit	Use to audit municipal systems and design an equality action plan.

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OSCE ODIHR – Gender-Responsive Governance Toolkit	https://www.osce.org/odihr/	Public administration, participation, governance	Tool kit & guidance	Improve municipal processes, and accountability with a gender lens.
CIB-UCLG Gender Toolkit for Local Governments	https://w.cib-uclg.org/gender-hub/gender-toolkit	Local government services, planning, budgets	Tool kit	Directly applicable to municipal departments and programmes.
Cities Alliance Women-Friendly Urban Planning Toolkit	https://www.citiesalliance.org/resources/publications/cities-alliance-knowledge/women-friendly-urban-planning-toolkit	Urban planning, public space, services	Tool kit (planning)	Use for neighbourhood plans, public realm, lighting, safety audits.
Metropolis Gender Equality in Metropolitan Contexts	https://www.metropolis.org/what-we-do/advocacy/gender-equality/	Urban governance, mobility, care, public space	Case studies & guidance	Peer learning and examples for city-scale strategies.

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POLIS Network – Gender & Mobility	https://www.polisnetwork.eu/topic/gender/	Transport, mobility, safety	Topic hub & reports	Support for transport departments on inclusive design and operations.
ITF (OECD) Gender Analysis Toolkit for Transport Policies	https://www.itf-oecd.org/itf-gender-analysis-toolkit-transport-policies	Transport policy projects	Tool & kit	Adopt for project appraisal, KPIs and user research.
UN Women Gender-Responsive Budgeting (GRB)	https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2010/1/gender-responsive-budgeting-in-practice-a-training-manual	Public finance, budgeting	Guide & training	Embed gender priorities in municipal budgets and M&E frameworks.
EIGE Gender-Responsive Public	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/grpp	Procurement, contracts	Tool kit	Integrate gender in tenders for services, works and infrastructure.

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Procurement
(GRPP) Toolkit

World Bank – <https://genderdata.worldbank.org/> Data & Data Context and Gender Data Portal indicators (global) port al benchmarking for local strategies; supports evidence-based policy.

UN Women Data Hub – Thematic Dashboards <https://data.unwomen.org/> Violence against women, SDGs, rights Data port al & dash boards Track VAW, participation and SDG progress for city action plans.

CHANGE – City Hub and Network for Gender Equity <https://www.citychange.org/resources/gender-equity-toolkit/> Municipal functions, equity Tool kit & play books Concrete municipal actions and templates for departments.

IUCN – Gender and Environment: GBV & <https://genderandenvironment.org/> Environment, climate, GBV Polic y brief s Integrate safety and gender into climate/resilience and public space projects.

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Environment Linkages			tool kits	
UN-Habitat Her City Toolbox	– https://hercity.unhabitat.org/	Urban planning, youth & girls' participation	Digital tool box	Use for co-design of neighbourhoods and public spaces.
UN-Habitat Gender Equality Action & Urban Safety resources	– https://unhabitat.org/	Urban safety, planning, governance	Guidance & reports	Policy framing and practical tools for safer, inclusive cities.
World Bank PPP Gender Toolkits	– https://ppp.worldbank.org/gender-toolkits	Infrastructure , procurement, PPPs	Tool kits	Apply to concessions and service contracts led by municipalities.
Council of Europe – Gender Equality Resources & Data	of https://www.coe.int/en/web/gender-equality	Policy frameworks, data sources	Portal & guidance	Align local policy with European standards; find data sources.

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<p>European Commission Gender Equality Strategy & Resources</p>	<p>https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality_en</p>	<p>EU policy, funding, mainstreaming</p>	<p>Policy & guidance</p>	<p>Inform local plans and connect to EU funding streams.</p>
<p>ICLEI – Gender, Climate & Resilience resources</p>	<p>https://iclei.org/</p>	<p>Climate action, resilience, equity</p>	<p>Guidance & case studies</p>	<p>Integrate gender in climate/energy plans and community programmes.</p>
<p>C40 Cities Inclusive Climate Action (Gender & Equity)</p>	<p>https://www.c40.org/what-we-do/scaling-up-climate-action/inclusive-climate-action/</p>	<p>Climate, equity, participation</p>	<p>Guidance & case studies</p>	<p>Inspiration and tools for city climate plans with a gender lens.</p>
<p>EUROCITIES Gender Equality in Cities</p>	<p>https://eurocities.eu/</p>	<p>Urban governance, services, participation</p>	<p>Network & resources</p>	<p>Peer exchange and examples from European municipalities.</p>

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U.S. Government – Gender-Based Violence (VAW) Evidence & Tools (as reference)	https://www.endvawnow.org/	Violence prevention, services	Tool kit & evidence	Design strategies coordinated services.	city	safety and local
WHO – Urban Health & Gender resources	https://www.who.int/health-topics/gender	Health, urban health equity	Guidance & data	Integrate primary care and urban health programmes.	gender	in prevention and health
European Initiative / URBACT – Gender Mainstreaming in Cities	https://urbact.eu/	Urban policy, local action planning	Case studies & tool kits	Hands-on EU-funded peer networks for local projects.	tools	and peer networks
Open Government Partnership (OGP) – Gender & Inclusion	https://www.opengovpartnership.org/topic/inclusion/	Transparency, participation, inclusion	Guidance & case	Use OGP approaches participatory policy design.	OGP	Local for gender

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<p>CEMR (Council of European Municipalities and Regions) – European Charter for Equality of Women and Men in Local Life</p>	<p>https://www.charter-equality.eu/</p>	<p>Local governance, equality commitments</p>	<p>Charter & implementation tools</p>	<p>Adopt the Charter and access tools for action planning and monitoring.</p>
<p>Global Network for Safer Cities (UN-Habitat) – Safer Cities for Women and Girls (Plan International)</p>	<p>https://unhabitat.org/network/global-network-on-safer-cities https://plan-international.org/protction-from-violence/safer-cities-guidelines/</p>	<p>Urban safety, GBV prevention in public spaces</p>	<p>Programme resources & tools</p>	<p>Implement local safety audits, design guidelines and partnerships.</p>

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<p>Rosa Luxemburg Foundation - Feminist cities</p>	<p>https://linx.rosalux.de/en/feminist-cities</p>	<p>Urban planning, youth & girls' participation</p>	<p>Programme resources & tools</p>	<p>Use for co-design of neighbourhoods and public spaces.</p>
<p>The Gendered City - Gendered City Index</p>	<p>https://genderedcity.org/gendered-city-index-gci</p>	<p>Data indicator, urban planning, urban safety, transport, walkability, governance</p>	<p>Tool kit & evidence</p>	<p>Context and benchmarking for local strategies; supports evidence-based policy.</p>

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5. Common Pitfalls and Context Adaptation

Summarise lessons mistakes to avoid, and guidance on adapting the framework to different city sizes, governance structures, and resource levels earned, typical

The work we have undertaken to establish the framework presented in this handbook has encountered a series of challenges, many of which are common and typical of experiences that have aimed to integrate GDEI into organisations, programmes and projects. Within INHABIT, we have been aware of these issues and, indeed, the framework and approach we propose aims to avoid some of them. The three pillars we build the GDEI handbook on, and the related Gendered Landscape framework, attempts to address some of the challenges that have historically been identified with the integration of gender considerations. For instance, in many cases, gender analysis is conducted late in the policy or project cycle, after key options have already been selected. Moreover, analysis tends to be descriptive, relying on sex-disaggregated data without sufficient attention to causal mechanisms, behavioural responses, or alternative scenarios. As a result, gender considerations are framed as peripheral risks rather than as factors that should shape core design choices. The proposed approach around the three pillars aims, instead, to embedding gender analysis early in project also by carrying out an ex-ante assessment and landscaping of institutional features and policies in order to identify gaps (including in terms of presence or lack of strong leadership and shared accountability) and areas of intervention. This will also allow to link tools to **decision points** (such as budgeting, procurement, staffing) and to ensure that adaptation is context-specific adaptation. Pillar III then ensures effective ex-post evaluation, which very often would require input from expert consultants.

In what follows we summarise the key challenges and pitfalls that are common to the integration of GDEI into projects and that have been also present in the work of INHABIT. For each of them, we identify the way it tends to manifest itself and the possible underlying causes. These pitfalls are not confined to specific projects or institutions; rather, they reflect systemic

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patterns in how GDEI analysis is often positioned, resourced, and incentivised. Therefore, understanding both their manifestations and underlying causes is critical for improving effectiveness.

Overall the key messages are that effective practice requires leadership commitment, institutional accountability, sufficient resourcing, and context-sensitive adaptation, ensuring tools inform decisions rather than merely document intentions. This is critical to translating intentions into effective analysis and tangible outcomes.

Late and Peripheral Application

Manifestations - Gender focused analyses (including gender mainstreaming, impact assessments etc.) are frequently undertaken after key policy or programme decisions have already been made. In such cases, gender considerations have little influence on core design choices, including objectives, delivery mechanisms, budgets, and timelines. Findings are often reframed as residual risks or mitigation measures rather than as factors shaping the selection between alternatives.

Underlying causes - This pattern reflects the institutional positioning of gender tools as approval stage or reporting requirements rather than as integral components of problem definition and option appraisal. Compressed preparation timelines and pressure to move quickly to approval further incentivise late stage analysis. Often, there are also no formal decision points requiring decision-makers to demonstrate how gender findings have influenced choices.

Solution - Integrate gender analysis early in the policy cycle and link it to key decision points, including budgeting and project approvals, so findings actively shape options and design choices.

Compliance-Driven and Tick-Box Approaches

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Manifestations - Analysis may be formally completed, but recommendations are weak, generic, or disconnected from implementation. Follow-up on identified gender risks or opportunities is limited, and learning across programmes is minimal.

Underlying causes - These patterns are driven by incentive structures that reward procedural compliance rather than substantive impact. In this way, organisations rationally prioritise speed and standardisation. The separation of gender reporting from core performance management systems further weakens incentives for meaningful engagement.

Solution - Align incentives and performance evaluation to reward the integration of gender findings into decision-making, not just completion of documentation.

Limited Analytical Depth and Causal Understanding

Manifestations - Many exercises remain descriptive, relying heavily on sex-disaggregated statistics without analysing causal mechanisms. Assessments frequently lack explicit theories of change, consideration of behavioural responses, or comparison of alternative policy or programme options. As a result, recommendations tend to be generic and insufficiently tailored to context.

Underlying causes - Limited analytical depth reflects a combination of time constraints, data limitations, and skills gaps. Analyses are often allocated insufficient resources relative to its stated importance. Perceptions that gender is an advocacy issue, and not a core analytical dimension, are still persistent. This all reduces investment in rigorous causal analysis.

Solutions - Invest in sector-specific capacity building, provide training on causal analysis and theories of change, and ensure dedicated time and resources for rigorous gender assessment.

Weak Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning

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Manifestations - Monitoring frameworks often include gender indicators, but these tend to focus on outputs (such as participation rates) rather than outcomes or impacts. Sex-disaggregated and intersectional data are inconsistently collected and rarely used. Opportunities for learning are therefore missed.

Underlying causes - Standardised indicator frameworks prioritise comparability across programmes at the expense of contextual relevance. Data systems are underfunded, and evaluation designs rarely prioritise gendered outcomes. In addition, weak links between monitoring data and decision-making processes limit the scope for adaptive management.

Solutions - Embed gender indicators within monitoring and evaluation systems, ensure collection and use of sex-disaggregated and intersectional data, and create feedback loops for adaptive management.

Over-Standardisation Across Contexts

Manifestations - Identical tools, templates, and indicators are applied across countries, sectors, and institutional settings with very different gender dynamics. Contextual information may be included descriptively, but it rarely influences design choices or implementation strategies.

Underlying causes - Harmonisation pressures and organisational preferences for standardisation encourage uniform approaches. Risk aversion and concern about losing comparability across programmes further discourage adaptation, even where contexts differ substantially.

Solution - Adapt tools to local contexts through contextual analysis; engage local stakeholders and tailor indicators and approaches to context-specific realities.

Insufficient Attention to Informal Institutions and Social Norms

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Manifestations - Efforts often focus on formal laws, policies, and institutional arrangements, while underestimating the role of informal norms and power relations.. As a result, interventions may have limited traction.

Underlying causes - Analytical frameworks frequently privilege formal policy levers and related established indicators. Limited integration of analysis of social norms constrains understanding of how inequality is reproduced in practice.

Solution - Incorporate analysis of informal norms and power structures, and design interventions that actively address social and behavioural barriers

Limited Intersectional Analysis

Manifestations - Women and men are often treated as homogeneous groups, masking differences related to income, ethnicity, age, disability, migration status, or location. This can result in benefits accruing primarily to relatively privileged groups, while marginalised populations remain excluded.

Underlying causes - Intersectional analysis is constrained by data limitations and by institutional pressure to keep analysis concise and manageable. Simplified frameworks are often favoured over more nuanced approaches.

Solution - Integrate intersectional analysis by using disaggregated data and participatory approaches to identify and address multiple forms of inequality.

Political Sensitivity and Backlash Risks

Manifestations - In politically sensitive environments, GDEI analysis and implementation may be symbolic rather than substantive, particularly where gender equality objectives lack strong political backing.

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Underlying causes - Weak enforcement mechanisms and the absence of formal requirements to respond to gender findings allow political considerations to override analytical conclusions.

Solutions - Build leadership and political buy-in by establishing formal accountability for responding to gender findings, and design strategies to mitigate backlash risks.

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Annexes

Annex 1 - Institutional Landscape Questionnaire

1. Political and Executive

• Members of city government by gender	/ Total members	
• Members of political parties by gender	Women / Total members	
• Is there a member of the government with specific role on equal opportunities?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
• Is there a member of the government with specific role on gender equality?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
• Are there stated political objectives on equal opportunities/gender equality?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
• Does the city government state targets and measures in terms of equal opportunities/gender equality?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No

2. Administration

a) Is promoting gender equality/equal opportunities part of the organisation general mandate?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
b) Is gender/equal opportunities mainstreaming integrated in the regulations of the city administration?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
c) Is there an administrative department on equal opportunities?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
I. If yes, how many staff it employs?		
		Answer 2d

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II.	If yes, what is the last annual budget allocated to that department?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d	
III.	If yes, what was the annual budget allocated to that department		
	one year before?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d <input type="checkbox"/>	
	No budget that year		
	two years before?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d <input type="checkbox"/>	
	No budget that year		
	three years before?	Answer 2d / Answer 2d <input type="checkbox"/>	
	No budget that year		
d)	Has the city administration an Equality Strategy in place?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
I.	If yes, what period does it cover?	Answer 2e	
II.	If yes, what areas does it cover:		
	i. Finance?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	ii. Social services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	iii. Transport?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	iv. Sport and Leisure?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	v. Culture?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	vi. Health?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	vii. Education?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	viii. Economic activities?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	ix. Environment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	x. Housing?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	xi. Urban and planning?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	xii. Work/Labour market?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	xiii. Other?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Answer 2e	
e)	Has the city administration, in the last five years, carried out any of the following:		
I.	Equality audit	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
		When last Answer 2f_I	When next Answer 2f_I

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II.	Equality impact assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_II	Answer 2f_II		
III.	Equality evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_III	Answer 2f_III		
IV.	Equality stakeholder consultations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_IV	Answer 2f_IV		
V.	Gender budgeting?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2f_V	Answer 2f_V		
f) Does the administration run surveys of the population in the following areas (whether separately or in combination)?							
		Yes	No	When last	When next	By gender	Any other group
I.	Finance?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_I	Answer 2g_I	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
II.	Social services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_II	Answer 2g_II	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
III.	Transport?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_III	Answer 2g_III	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
IV.	Sport and Leisure?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_IV	Answer 2g_IV	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V.	Culture?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_V	Answer 2g_V	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
VI.	Health?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_VI	Answer 2g_VI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
VII.	Education?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_VII	Answer 2g_VII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
VIII.	Economic activities?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_VIII	Answer 2g_VIII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
IX.	Environment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_IX	Answer 2g_IX	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
X.	Housing?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_X	Answer 2g_X	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
XI.	Urban and planning?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_XI	Answer 2g_XI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
XII.	Work/Labour market?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_XII	Answer 2g_XII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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XIII.	Other?	Please specify <input type="checkbox"/>	Answer 2g_XIII	Answer 2g_XIII	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
g) Has the administration collected any gender disaggregated data in any of the following area in the last five years?						
I.	Population and demography?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
II.	Transport?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
III.	Health?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
IV.	Education?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
V.	Culture?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
VI.	Sport?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
VII.	Environment?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
VIII.	Housing?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
IX.	Economic activities?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
X.	Urban and Planning?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
XI.	Work/Labour market?		<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No
XII.	Other?		Please specify		<input type="checkbox"/>	No

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Annex 2 - How to represent the Institutional Landscape

The Questionnaire in Annex 1 collects a range of information and data for the six dimensions of the Pillar. Most of the questions ask for the presence (or absence) of specific GDEI tools and the specific areas covered. To analyse these data, we converted each answer into a numeric value. Therefore, each positive answer takes the value 1, while a negative answer is coded 0. When several items are grouped together by dimension, all dimensional values are summed up together and this sum is divided by the total number of items in the respective dimension. This ensures that the final dimensional value is between 0 and 1. We can interpret this score as either the average number of positive answers per item in the dimension or the share of positive answers in the dimension. Only three questions result in numeric values: these are the gender compositions of governing assemblies, the gender composition of local workforces; the annual budget of GDEI departments. We need to convert these values into a 0-1 range as per other variables/dimensions above. Gender compositions are defined as the share of women in a position, so we can transform such share into an inequality measure that is bounded between 0 and 1, with 1 indicating no inequality. More formally, we compute the absolute difference between the share of women in a position and the ideal equal distribution (i.e. 50%) divided by 50. This can be interpreted as the relative change in women's share necessary to achieve an equal distribution. Then, we subtract this value from 1 so that it is monotonically increasing and has its maximum at 1. Note that, with such formulation, an excess of women is treated similarly as an excess of men. We have now transformed all scores into variables between 0 and 1. We sum all of them by dimension, and because not all dimensions have the same number of items, we rescale all dimension indices so that they have the same maximum. Formally, the rescaling factors are computed for each dimension as the maximum theoretical value in all dimensions

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divided by the maximum theoretical value in the rescaled dimension. These computed indices can then be plotted into radar diagrams as the one shown in Figure 1.

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Annex 4 - Behavioural Game Handbook for cities.

Table of content

- I. General objectives
- II. Behavioural games for IN-HABIT
 - a) Behavioural games at different stages
 - b) Preferences, stereotypes, and cooperation
 - c) Behavioural games and VIS
 - d) Common-Pool Resources games
- III. Logistics
 - a) Preparation
 - b) Games logistics
 - c) Instructions for experimenters
 - d) Instructions for participants
 - e) Ethics
 - f) Preliminary protocol

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General objectives

- We will use a mix of behavioural games for understanding preferences in each of the different cities and for testing targeted interventions with a G&D approach
 - Run behavioural games to elicit preferences and find targeted solutions for collective problems
 - Study how to foster cooperation using CPR games
 - Reveal stereotypes and evaluate solutions
 - Test nudges to promote behaviour change

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Behavioural games at different stage of the project

- INHABIT will provide innovative ways to design, implement and appraise policy interventions (e.g. simple heuristics, hyperbolic discounting, use of social norms, nudges and behavioural games).
- Behavioural games will be employed to serve different functions at different stages of the work programme:
 - Studying preferences and decision-making: incentivized experiments to reveal decision making using within subjects design
 - Evaluating the impact of new measures: between subjects design with control and treatment groups

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The role of preferences in fostering cooperation

- In the early stages of the project, games will be used as a method of preference elicitation from a broad sample of citizens in each of the cities (recruited via the community activators and neighbourhood observers).
- There is a long tradition in the use of behavioural games in the elicitation of preferences (Chaudhuri, 2009), especially around the allocation of public goods and resources (Andreoni, 1995), and they can be used to help understand the circumstances under which more equitable distributions of goods are likely to be accepted, and the key drivers at play in these circumstances.
- The preferences elicited will then help building a picture of the key drivers of behaviour and barriers to change in each of the focal communities and inform the design of the INHABIT-APP.
- In this phase of the project, behavioural games will be integrated with the baseline study on IHW carried by partner ISIM as well as with the co-design of VIS carried by the pilot cities and TSR. In fact these three processes will be performed in parallel, by involving the same group of local community representatives (“observers”) and using integrated methodologies.

The role of preferences in fostering cooperation

- *Present biased individuals* (eg. Hyperbolic discounting) may be less likely to perceive the long term advantages associated to cooperation and the adoption of sustainable lifestyle (Andreoni and Sprenger, 2012)
- Social norms and trust play a significant role in cooperation in addition to the fact that some people may be '*conditional cooperators*'. (Fehr and Fischbacher, 2004; Gächter, 2007)
- The way information is provided and the framing of uncertain future outcomes will impact differently individuals' willingness to act pro socially
 - Important to understand the behavioural characteristics of each community to design targeted interventions
 - Behavioural games will help to reveal those characteristics and inform future solutions

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The role of Stereotypes in Cooperation

- Stereotyping might influence individuals' perception of cooperation, from free riders to high contributors and affect the productivity of the group in managing CPR. (Andreoni and Petrie, 2008)
- Repeated CPR games offer a setting where stereotyping is possible (groups with several participants). Participants will have the opportunity to confront their expectations of behavior (based on stereotype) and if they match observed behavior. Participation in subsequent rounds will inform about how people adjust to their revision of stereotypes.
- We will run games to reveal stereotypes on gender and diversity and how people react/adjust to them in repeated interactions

Behavioural games for understanding barriers to cooperation and how to design VIS and INHABIT-APP

- The games have been co-designed to help reveal the perspective of marginalized target groups and those who should cooperate with them in the realization of the VIS for each city.
- In each city, the implementation of behavioural games will take place in the local language and will be facilitated by the LCAs and dedicated helpers to be recruited specifically for the purpose of running the games.
- The sample of participants will include a representative range of citizens with PCs who are often excluded in traditional sampling, by targeting citizens via services with which they are already engaged e.g. surgeries, schools, retirement communities. Games will be made available in paper version so as not to exclude those who might not have access to mobile technology.

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Behavioural games to test solutions

- In the later stages of the project (Yrs 4 & 5), behavioural games will perform a different function. Here we will instead employ games that are designed to help supporting and maintaining behaviour change.
- In these games we will build on the work done across the programme in understanding a “day in the life” of individual citizens (especially those within designated at-risk or marginal groups), to develop games that support perspective taking.
- These games will additionally be tailored to the specific context examined in each of the city focus concept (culture, food, animals, art and environment) ensuring that they are as closely aligned with the key inclusion goals as possible, taking into account the geographical, cultural and psychological context as much as possible and making use of the INHABIT-APP prototype.
- This includes testing solutions to promote the adoption of sustainable lifestyle such as nudges, reminder and frequency of reminders, information framing (figures, ranking, peer information) etc...

Common-pool resource games

- **Common-pool resources** are goods characterized by **low excludability** (difficulties to prevent that other individuals use the good) and **high subtractability** (the availability of the good decreases when the good is used/consumed).
 - e.g. fish banks, forests, water...
 - In IN-HABIT, **health and well-being**
- **Common-pool resource games**
 - Artificial situation where players have to manage common-pool resources. They may choose how much of the CPR to extract for their own good at the expense of the other players and their ability to extract again in the future.

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Common-pool resources game

What are we testing

Competitive vs cooperative norms

- To what extent nudging social norms could increase cooperation within cities?
- How to best design your message to foster cooperation?

	Control	Treatment 1	Treatment 2
Step 1	Nudge 'neutral' norm 'what people in the city do'	Nudge 'cooperative' norm 'what people from <u>your</u> group do'	Nudge 'competitive' norm 'what people from the <u>other</u> group do'
Step 2	Common Pool Resource Game		
Step 3	City Intervention		
Step 4	Evaluation		

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Next steps

- Work with cities to co-design behavioural games TAILORED to their interventions (particularly around promotion of soft-solutions)
- Provide logistics support, training and resources for running the games

Preparation logistics

- Indicative number of participants: 150-200 per city (minimum 50 per group, C, T1, T2)
- Funds cover:
 - participation fees (e.g. mobility, child care, and other opportunity costs / special needs)
 - show up fee
 - game winnings up to 50 euros pp (including show-up fee)
 - Helpers
 - Games materials
- In advance of sessions materials will be translated into the local language. Two translators will enable back translation, in order to make sure translation introduces no biases.
- **Recruitment and training of helpers (at least two weeks before)**
 - 1 helper per 10 participants => ~6 helpers in total
 - Helpers will help with recruitment of participants, organization of spaces, running the games and entering the data collected (in spreadsheet prepared by UREAD)
- Recruitment of participants (tailored to target groups of each cities) (at least one week ahead, remember special needs participants need more time)
- **Organization of spaces (at least two weeks ahead)**
- Assignment of participants to groups (groups need to be diverse)
 - Groups have to represent all the targeted personal characteristics
- One member of UREAD will travel to assist and help coordinate the games

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Games logistics - Single round CPR game

- 30 participants per session
- 3 coordinators (one main coordinator + 2 coordinators)
- pen and paper for the participants
- numbers from 1 to 30 to identify participants and ensure anonymity (numbers to be reported on each individual answer sheets)
- one room with larger capacity, depending on the setting (space should be enabled between participant to facilitate privacy).
- 30mn-1h per session, up to 4 sessions per day
 - Comprises the CPR game
 - A sociodemographic survey
 - A short survey on pillar 2 gender landscape

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Instructions sheet for experimenters

Instructions sheet for experimenters

Materials for 30 participants:

- 30 consent forms
- 30 Pencils
- 30 numbered questionnaires
- 30 ID numbers
- 30 numbered envelope (for payment)
- 30 debriefing forms
- 30 evaluation forms
- Administrator's instructions
- 1 reserved room

Instructions sheet for experimenters

Introduction:

Thank you for agreeing to participate in our research.

1) **Hand participants the consent form.** Please read this consent form which describes the study. You should feel free to ask any questions. If you agree to the terms of the research, sign the consent form. After they are done, collect the consent forms and place in a large, manila envelope.

2) **Distribute the numbered questionnaires and pencils.** Before answering the questions, please read the instructions to the study. If you have any questions, raise your hand and a helper will come to you. Remember there are no right or wrong answers. Only your decision matters. This is a private and anonymous questionnaire, so please answer it privately. When you are finished, return the questionnaire to me.

3) **Collect the materials and hand participants the debriefing form.** Be sure to collect the forms in a manner that ensures confidentiality. You might have the participants place them in a large manila envelope, or collect them "face down" so that you cannot view responses. Please read and sign the debriefing form. When you are finished, I will collect them. Collect signed debriefing forms and place in a separate, large, manila envelope. Thank you for your participation. Feel free to take a duplicate debriefing form with you if you came to have one. If you want the participant to keep a copy of the debriefing form, come prepared with two copies per participant.

4) **Instruct participants to complete a Research Evaluation Form online.** Thank you again for participating in our study. We welcome you to complete an evaluation form to provide our department with feedback regarding this particular study and the experiment(s). Research Evaluation Forms are now available online.

5) **While participant complete the debriefing form and the research evaluation form online, 2 coordinators compute the results to work out individual earnings.**

Instructions - double-click

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Instructions sheet for participants (to be read by LCAs to all participants)

Instructions sheet for participants

You are about to participate in a survey session about your preferences. For your participation, you will be paid a show-up fee of €7. In addition, you may receive some additional money based on your choices and the choice of others during the experiment. Your answers will remain anonymous. For that purpose, you have been assigned a unique ID number. This ID number appears on the questionnaire you have received.

Your earnings will be given to you after the session in cash in a closed envelope by a third party, to preserve confidentiality. You will only need to present your ID number to collect your earnings (the one attached to the questionnaire). This survey is personal and we ask you to remain silent during the whole time devoted to the survey. There is neither right nor wrong answers. We are only interested in your individual preferences. Fill in the questions as personally and accurately as you can. If you have any question, raise your hand and wait for a helper to come by you.

You will soon receive the survey and your ID number. Please do not start writing until you will be instructed to do so.

Participants - double-click

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Participant Information Sheet

Research Project: Inclusive Health And wellBeing in small and medium size cities (IN-HABIT)
Project Team Members: Ft. Marina Della Giusta (Principal Investigator), Dr. Sophie Clot, Dr. Florent Dubois, and Dr. Rachel McCreay

We would like to invite you to take part in a research study about public goods.

What is the study?

The study is being conducted by the University of Reading. IN-HABIT is a Horizon Europe research project that aims at improving health and well-being in 4 European cities (Globovia, Niza, Luca, Riga). Each city realises one of their neighbourhoods with a new public good to reach this goal. In your city, IN-HABIT is changing to improve health and well-being through it.

Why have I been chosen to take part?

You are living in the neighbourhood being realized or you are a potential user of the infrastructure being deployed. As such, you are directly concerned about how this public good will be used and maintained, and we would like to understand how and why you will use it or not.

Do I have to take part?

It is entirely up to you whether you participate. You may also withdraw your consent to participation at any time during the project, without any repercussions to you, by contacting the Project Principal Investigator, Dr Marina Della Giusta, Tel: 0118 378 3068, email: m.d.giusta@reading.ac.uk.

What will happen if I take part?

You will be asked to complete a short survey and will participate in a social game. You will be given a show-up fee to compensate for your participation and you may earn an additional monetary reward at the end of the game.

What are the risks and benefits of taking part?

The information you give will remain confidential and will only be seen by the research team listed at the start of this letter. This study is entirely anonymous. You will not be identifiable in any published report resulting from the study.

Participants in similar studies have found it interesting to take part. You will learn about your own unconscious biases and new methods for you to have better and more inclusive teaching practices and environment. We anticipate that the findings of the study will be useful for teachers and learning staff in planning how they teach and/or support learners.

What will happen to the data?

Any data collected will be held in strict confidence and no real names will be used in this study or in any subsequent publications. No identifiers linking you to the study will be included in any sort of report that might be published. Participants will be assigned a number and will be referred to by that number in all records. The data will be stored securely on a password-protected computer and only the research team will have access to them. At the

end of the study, the data will be securely anonymized or pseudonymized so that it will erase permanently any way to identify individuals. The results of the study will be presented at national and international conferences, and in written reports and articles. We can send you electronic copies of these publications if you wish.

What happens if I change my mind?

You can change your mind at any time without any repercussions. During the research, you can stop completing the activities at any time. If you change your mind after data collection has ended, we will discard your data.

Who has reviewed the study?

The project has been subject to Ethical Review and has been approved by the ethics committee of the University of Reading to ensure all data collection, analysis and storage are in compliance with GDPR (you can check details here: <https://uk.europa.eu/>). The University has the appropriate measures in place. Full details are available on request.

What happens if something goes wrong?

In the unlikely case of concern or complaint, you can contact Professor Marina Della Giusta email: m.d.giusta@reading.ac.uk

Where can I get more information?

If you would like more information, please contact Professor Marina Della Giusta email: m.d.giusta@reading.ac.uk

We do hope that you will agree to your participation in the study. If you do, please sign the associated consent form and wait for the coordinator's instructions.

Thank you for your time.

Information sheet - double-click

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Consent form

Research Project: Inclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size αTies (IN-HABIT)

Participant Consent Form

I have read the Information Sheet about the project and received a copy of it.
I understand what the purpose of the project is and what is required of me. All my questions have been answered.

Name of participant: _____

Consent form - double-click

Please tick as appropriate:

- I consent to completing a questionnaire.
- I consent to participating in a social game.
- I consent to completing a feedback form.
- I consent to be contacted for a follow up survey in 3-6 months.

Signed: _____

Date: _____

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Preliminary Protocol

A/Control 8/75

Anonymous questionnaire 8/75
Please answer this questionnaire in private and as accurately as possible. There are no right or wrong answers.

Thank you for taking part in this survey. This survey is entirely anonymous and voluntary (you are free to withdraw at any time). You have been allocated a random number at the top of the questionnaire and on the corner of the sheet. Please scratch the number in the corner of the sheet. You will receive your payment which will be calculated based on your answers in this questionnaire, at the end of the session upon presentation of this number.

A sum of 30 euros has been allocated to you for this event: 20 euros to cover for your participation and 10 euros to be used as tokens in the game below, which could be either invested towards the community or that you can keep for yourself. If you invest tokens, you can earn from 0 up to 30 euros in addition to your 20 euros. You will then end the game with total earnings ranging from 20 euros up to 50 euros. Or you can choose to not invest tokens and end the game with 30 euros. This decision is entirely yours and we guarantee anonymity. The privacy of your decision is ensured by the number you have been allocated.

You have 300 tokens (5 euros = 30 tokens) to play the game.

This game is about investing in a (300 euro) project. The specific type of project will depend on the fund collected. The project will benefit the entire community, but will target in particular (people with very low incomes).

There are 4 stages in this game:

- Stage 1: starting the project.
- Stage 2 & 3: covering the project.
- Stage 4: benefits from the project.

At the end of the game, depending on your decisions as well as decisions from other people in your group, you will receive the benefits from the project. This benefit will depend on the state of the project, which relies on your decision and your group decision over the 3 stages. Each group is made of 5 individuals. You all have 300 tokens each.

At stage 4, the total number of tokens invested in the project from all members of the group is tripled, and then shared out equally between the group members. For example, if together you invest 1200 tokens altogether over the 3 stages, you will each receive a gain of 720 tokens (1200*3/5) participants) in addition to your participation fee, so 44€ extra total (36€ from the game + 8€).

You have 300 tokens in total and you can invest up to 300 tokens at each stage. Your final gain will depend from the state of the project.

Stage 1: Starting the project.

How many tokens you invest at this stage: _____ (from 0 to 300)

How many tokens, on average, do you think other people in your group have invested in stage 1? _____ (from 0 to 300)

Stage 2: Raising the project.

For this second stage, we ask you to invest tokens depending on how many tokens other members of the group have invested in stage 1.

Total tokens invested in Stage 1 by your group	How many tokens you invest at stage 2 (0-100)
High: <100	_____
Medium: 200-300	_____
Low: <200	_____

How many tokens, on average, do you think other people in your group have invested in stage 2? _____ (from 0 to 300)

Stage 3: The maintenance stage - looking after the garden.

For this third stage, we ask you to invest tokens depending on how many tokens other members of the group have invested over stage 1 & stage 2.

Total tokens invested by your group - Stage 1 + Stage 2	How many tokens you invest at stage 3 (0-100)
Very High: >800	_____
High: 600-800	_____
Medium: 400-600	_____
Low: 200-400	_____
Very Low: <200	_____

How many tokens, on average, do you think other people in your group have invested in stage 3? _____ (from 0 to 300)

Stage 4:

This table shows your individual earnings depending on how many tokens you have invested as a group. The total contribution will be calculated by adding up the sum invested in stage 1 and the corresponding sum collected as a group in stage 2 and 3. For example, if the total group contribution at Stage 1 is 200, then the corresponding amount invested in Stage 2 for the 'Medium' level will be added up for the 5 members of the group.

Total contribution	Individual average contribution per group	Individual gain in euros	Total payment
_____	_____	_____	_____

Protocol - double-click

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

17/03/2022

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Disclaimer: The content of this document does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union and in no way anticipates the European Commission's future policy in this area. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the author(s).

Annex 5 - Replication Sheet

Institutional Landscape Analysis (Pillar I)

Case study: IN-HABIT – Córdoba

What

Institutions shaping how GDEI is:

- regulated
- resourced
- implemented
- monitored

Why

GDEI fails when:

- mandates stay symbolic
- no resources follow
- accountability is weak

How

8w Institutional survey [Go to Annex 1](#)

0.5w Index construction [Go to Annex 2](#)

0.5w Radar visualisation [Go to Annex 2](#)

1w SWOT reflection

Total duration: **10 weeks**

Six diagnostic dimensions

- Stakeholder involvement
- Political commitment
- Legal framework
- Resources & structures
- Accountability
- Data & knowledge

Institutional profile – Córdoba

Scores normalised on a 0–5 scale

Córdoba – SWOT-style interpretation

Strengths

- Strong legal mandate for GDEI
- Clear quantified equality targets
- Dedicated councillor for equality and gender
- Equality strategy covering 10 policy areas

Weaknesses

- No evaluation of GDEI impacts
- Very limited use of independent research
- Weak stakeholder involvement
- No dedicated GDEI budget or department
- Monitoring limited to gender budgeting

Key insight:

Political and legal commitment is strong, but implementation capacity, evidence use and monitoring remain fragile.

Replication takeaway

Combine surveys, indices, visuals and stakeholder mapping to expose where institutional ambition stops short of delivery.

Next steps: choosing the right tool

Do you have a clear baseline assessment of your institutional capacity for GDEI? (mandate, structures, resources, accountability, data)

Do you have sufficient resources and data to implement and monitor change? (budget, staff time, data standards, access to datasets)

Do you need a time-bound plan to address identified gaps? (owners, deliverables, deadlines, monitoring)

Are you designing or revising a concrete policy or programme?

Participatory gender audit

See GDEI Handbook p.35

Gender mainstreaming architecture, Stakeholder mapping

See GDEI Handbook p.37

GDEI action plan

See GDEI Handbook p.40

Pillar II – Policies

See GDEI Handbook p.10

Annex 6 - Replication Sheet

Behavioural Game for Inclusive Outcomes

Pillar III – Welfare Outcomes | Case study: IN-HABIT – Córdoba

<p>What is replicated</p> <p>A behavioural game to measure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cooperation trust collective action contribution to common goods 	<p>Why behavioural games</p> <p>Surveys miss behaviour.</p> <p>Games reveal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> real choices social norms hidden constraints 	<p>Key outcome logic</p> <p>Behaviour is an outcome.</p> <p>Games help assess:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> inclusion trust-building interactions with social norms
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Behavioural game – core design	
<p>Game type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common Pool Resource game Multiple rounds Individual decisions, group consequences 	<p>What is observed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution levels Free-riding Cooperation and discrimination Response to incentives

Concrete implementation: Córdoba	
<p>Who participated</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residents of Las Palmeras, a marginalised neighbourhood Residents of Córdoba <p>What common-pool resource</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multifunctional green space 	<p>What the game revealed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher contribution to the common pool resource when it benefits the general population rather than the marginalized group. Participants adjust their own contribution depending on the collective contribution Gender gaps: men free-ride if the collective contribution is high enough, women reduce their contribution less strongly than men when collective contributions diminish

How to replicate Go to Annex 4									
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trained facilitator Neutral space 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple materials Clear rules 								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethical safeguards Inclusive recruitment 									
Process timeline									
<table border="0" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 12.5%;">Design 6–8 w</td> <td style="width: 12.5%;">Preparation 4 w</td> <td style="width: 12.5%;">Implementation 0.5 w</td> <td style="width: 12.5%;">Data 3 w</td> <td style="width: 12.5%;">Analyses 6–8 w</td> <td style="width: 12.5%;">Reporting 1 w</td> </tr> </table>	Design 6–8 w	Preparation 4 w	Implementation 0.5 w	Data 3 w	Analyses 6–8 w	Reporting 1 w	<p>Next steps:</p> <table border="0" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">Policy revision</td> <td style="width: 50%;">Action plan</td> </tr> </table>	Policy revision	Action plan
Design 6–8 w	Preparation 4 w	Implementation 0.5 w	Data 3 w	Analyses 6–8 w	Reporting 1 w				
Policy revision	Action plan								

Replication takeaway
Behavioural games turn inclusion into observable outcomes and provide valuable insights to correct policy flaws.